

A COMPARATIVE AND DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF FILM TITLE TRANSLATIONS AND APPELLATIVE EFFECT TRANSFER INTO CROATIAN AND GERMAN

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Abstract

Studies of film title translations remain scant to this day. The existing studies mainly focus on investigating the sources of difficulties during the translation process. Although the studies employ different analytical approaches, the conclusion in almost all investigations is that the decisive objective during the translation process is the transfer or production of the appellative effect. This study investigates which strategies are employed during translation into Croatian and German and why, as well as possible diachronic changes in the choice of translation strategies. We created a corpus of 935 film titles from 1923 to 2017 and their translations into Croatian and German, which we first classified as direct translation, free translation, transcreation or transcription, and finally we quantitatively and qualitatively analysed the data. Our results show considerable differences between the two subcorpora in the choice of translation strategies and motivation, as well as in the patterns of diachronic change. Furthermore, correlations with specific cultural-historical processes are observed.

1. Introduction

Film titles have been understood as having a prominent role in one's perception, thus also in one's understanding, of a film. A title is defined as a paratext type, as are prefaces, postfaces, dedications, remarks and subheadings (Genette, 1989: 8–10). A paratext is an addition to the text which can have various functions, such as guiding the reader's interpretation. Titles are easily recognisable visually, as they normally precede the text; they are significantly shorter than the text itself, and

they are graphically pronounced (Iannelli 1998: 26). Šidiškytė and Tamulaitienė (2013: 71) assert that film titles are “the most salient and eye-catching part and would rightly deserve a more extensive and systematic linguistic research”. A title is thus given an important communicational role through which it mediates between the addressee of the text to which it belongs and the text it entitles (Peña-Cervel 2016: 305).

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Functions of titles

During linguistic production, every sender performs a speech act that can be described in terms of several linguistic functions. In his organon model, Bühler (1934: 28) differentiates between three prominent functions of the linguistic sign: the representative function, which stands for a link between the linguistic sign and the referent in an extralinguistic reality, the expressive function, through which a link is formed between the realised message and the sender by transmitting the mental states of the sender, and the appellative function, which stimulates the addressee into action. All three functions are present during communication, and one of them always dominates. These linguistic functions, proposed by Bühler and Jakobson, have been successfully applied to titles in the field of translation studies.

Nord (1995: 264), for example, discriminates between three essential and three optional functions. The essential functions include the distinctive, the metatextual and the phatic function. The distinctive function relates to the uniqueness of the title in a particular culturally specific corpus. Iannelli (1998: 31) notes, however, that in some cases the expansion of the title is necessary for it to maintain its distinctive function. Thus sometimes titles of homonymous literary works such as *Satires* or *Novellas* need to include the name of the author or epoch, or some other name. Iannelli further mentions that titles of similar expression have been known to cause interference, such as with the titles of two works of Immanuel Kant *Kritik der reinen Vernunft* ‘critique of pure reason’ and *Kritik der praktischen Vernunft* ‘critique of practical reason’.

Moreover, information about the genre is conveyed through Nord's metatextual function since it has been noted in translation research that the formation of titles and their translations depend on the genre's conventions of a particular market.

The phatic function enables the creation of the communication channel and also message consolidation (Nord 1995: 264; Katnić-Bakaršić 1999: 3). The phatic function of a title can have a prominent role even in the absence of the text, which is important for maintaining the consumer's interest in the product (Boucheri 2008: 30).

Optional functions include, according to Nord (1995), the referential, the expressive and the appellative function. The referential function refers to information directly transmitted through the title. The sender's mental states are relayed through the expressive function. It has been noted that specific lexical-semantic structures can enhance the expressive effect, such as diminutives, superlatives, verbs in the first person, lexemes with salient emotional connotations, possessive pronouns etc. (Nord 2011: 64). The appellative function encourages the addressee to act (Nord 2011: 62–3).

Most studies concerned with film title translation have noted that the appellative effect is given the foremost attention during title production and translation (Schubert 2004; Limon 2012; Peña-Cervel 2016; Surdyk and Urban 2016; Jutronic and Karabatic 2016). In the context of film titles and their translations, the appellative effect relates to the efforts aimed at encouraging as many people as possible to watch the film. It is therefore no wonder that film title translation has been associated with skopos theory (Schubert 2004: 240). Although relatively clear boundaries between specific linguistic functions, or rather effects, have been made above, it has also been proposed that virtually all linguistic functions of titles have the potential of enhancing the appellative effect (Leonardi 2011: 10). An increase in the metatextual effect, by for example adding genre key words, and in the expressive effect, by adding emotionally salient lexemes, has been correlated with an increase in the appellative effect (Leonardi 2011: 17). Some authors have even gone so far as to say that film title translation is nothing more than appellative effect

transfer (Schubert 2004: 241), while Jutronić and Karabatić (2016: 103) have equated film title translation strategies with marketing strategies.

2.2 *The process of film title translation*

The amount of shared knowledge about the process of film title translation has been modest at best. While it is clear that film texts are translated by professional translators, the role of the translator in film title translation seems to be quite tenuous. Studies of film title translations have not been particularly concerned with the translation process, although such information probably would shed some light on the apparent appellative behaviour of film title translations. Most studies claim that film titles are translated first and foremost, or even solely, by film distributors (Jutronić and Karabatić 2016: 103; Limon 2012: 8; Peña-Cervel 2016: 307). While sources of such information have mostly been unclear, Limon states that his knowledge about the translation process in Slovenia stems from conversations with four film distributors and the Slovenian public broadcaster *Radiotelevizija Slovenija*. Limon notes that cinema film titles are translated mostly by distributors, while the translation of film titles shown on television falls within the domain of the broadcaster. However, in some cases an already existing title translation is adopted, for example when the film text is based on a literary work (Limon 2012: 9). Šidiškytė and Tamulaitienė (2013: 75) have also observed that a title translation into one language can determine the translation into another language. The authors exemplify this with the film title *Arbitrage* (2012), which was translated into Lithuanian as *Apgaulinga aistra* 'deceptive passion' and into Russian as *Порочная страсть* 'vicious passion' whereby the authors assume that the Russian translation influenced the one made in Lithuania. A similar situation has been detected in Slovenian translations, where in a limited number of cases German translations seem to determine the final form of the title translation in Slovenian (Limon 2012: 9).

In order to examine the process of film title translation in Croatia and Germany we talked to Branimira Borčić Nemeč, head of the Translation Department at the Croatian Radio and Television (HRT), which is the Croatian national broadcasting

company, Henning Bochert, from the translation agency Bochert Translations in Berlin, and Timm Oberwelland, from the independent distribution company TOBIS Film GmbH in Berlin. We attempted to contact Croatian film distributors as well, but our calls were not returned. Borčić Nemeč states that translators at the Croatian Radio and Television are actively involved in title translation. The translator suggests potential title translations; however, the final translation is chosen by the editor of the film department. A language editor is also involved in the process. Borčić Nemeč notes that there are specific rules at the Croatian Radio and Television limiting possible translations. For example, foreign words are avoided when possible, normative accuracy is praised, while puns and wordplay are encouraged. Translators also seek to be as faithful to the original as possible and to maintain a connection to the film text. If a film title has already been translated, a translator may suggest a new translation if they have valid arguments. This is, however, typically not the case if a translation has been listed in the *Film Encyclopedia (Filmska enciklopedija; Peterlić 1986a; Peterlić 1986b)* published by the Miroslav Krleža Institute of Lexicography; such translations can only be modified in exceptional cases.

Bochert claims that, as a translator of feature films for Netflix, he has not wielded any influence on title translation, which is controlled by marketing. Bochert notes that before the 1980s film titles were mostly directly or freely translated, while today the original titles are often transcribed and adopted as translations. In addition, the strategy of using expanded titles – which includes a German addition alongside the original English title – is widely used in Germany. Bochert connects this strategy with advertising, considering the fact that title addition has the function of a slogan for the film, but it is also connected with, as he states, the tendency to create a balance between the great influence of English in Germany and the status of German as the official and national language. Given that foreign films are mostly dubbed, viewers do not find this strategy unusual because it is perceived as a minor intervention on the part of the translator from the perspective of the viewer when the film is already dubbed in its entirety. Bochert also mentions the role of film studios when choosing a translation strategy. Studios sometimes require that the title be left unchanged, which must be respected by the distributors and others who are involved. Wordplay is used in Germany, as it is by the Croatian Radio and

Television, whenever possible. A TV broadcaster in Germany may change an existing title translation, as is the case in Croatia, even if the film was already shown in cinemas. Bochert mentions the title of the film *The Astronaut's Wife* (Ravich 1999), which has two translations in Germany, one for the cinema (*Die Frau des Astronauten* 'the astronaut's wife') and another for television (*Die Frau des Astronauten – Das Böse hat ein neues Gesicht* 'the astronaut's wife – evil has a new face'). The first translation is a direct translation of the original, while the other has an addition alongside the direct translation of the original title. The title addition gives extra information about the genre and the plot of the film, thus fulfilling its advertising function, which is to attract a large number of viewers.

In order to determine how film distributors decide on the translation of a film title, we consulted Timm Oberwelland from the independent distribution company TOBIS Film GmbH based in Berlin. The company deals in the distribution of German and foreign films screened in Austria, Germany and Switzerland. The advertising department of the company, which includes no translators, decides on the translation of a film title, thus confirming the minor or even non-existent role of professional translators in the process of film title translation. Oberwelland explains that the company buys screening rights for films in duration from 15 to 20 years. The license is valid for screening films on all distribution channels: the cinema, television and the Internet. Each year they buy the rights for 15 films. The contract, which the company makes with film producers, determines all commercial aspects of the film on the new market: the film poster, the advertising budget and the film title, which means that the licensor must agree with the chosen poster and title. The distributors are also responsible for the subtitling and dubbing for the German market. This part of the work is done by translators employed as freelancers. Last year they translated titles using the transcreation strategy [e.g. *Viceroy's House* (2017) > *Der Stern von Indien* 'the star of India'], direct translation [e.g. *Paris Can Wait* (2016) > *Paris kann warten*] and transcription [e.g. *Bad Moms* (2016)].

The influence of the English language on the German market is related to social networks, through which the potential viewers often hear of a film for the first time and of its original title, which is usually in English. Therefore, distributors sometimes

decide to keep the original English title since its translation would be a bad marketing move, especially if it is a film featured in foreign and German media for winning a prestigious award. Oberwelland states the example of the film *12 Years a Slave* (2013), which was shown in Germany under the exact same title because the distributors thought that the appellative function was more powerful when using the original title.

The choice of a translation can also be influenced by the title translation of the literary work the film is based on. If a film is based on a book which was translated into German prior to the distribution of the book-based film, distributors will use the book's title translation as in the example of *P. S. I Love You* (2007), which was translated into German as *P. S. Ich liebe dich* 'P. S. I love you'.

When translating film titles, distributors seek to transfer and, if possible, amplify the appellative effect. Oberwelland thus mentions the film *The Last Word* (2017) where the title was not directly translated into German although this was possible; it was rather distributed under the title *Zu guter Letzt* 'at long last'. The decision to change the title was made because the direct translation would have the negative connotation of finality which creates the mental image of the ultimate piece in a sequence, whereas the German title translation has a more positive connotation since it only signifies the end of a well-rounded unit.

The advertising function of a title determines the success of a film on the market. Therefore, it can happen that a film is more successful on a foreign market than on its original market thanks to a more explicit title. This can be seen in the example of *A Little Chaos* (2014), which was commercially more successful on the German market. Oberwelland attributes this fact to the transcreation of the title into *Die Gärtnerin von Versailles* 'the gardener of Versailles' which expresses the film's plot more explicitly and strengthens the appellative effect of the title.

3. Approaches to the study of film title translation

Early studies concerned with titles mostly examined the titles of literary works, especially novels. Film titles were only sometimes taken into account, mostly to establish a comparative perspective. These studies compared literary works and film

titles with the titles of scientific papers (Bouchehri 2008: 33). Despite the early involvement of film titles in title research and the apparent progress in translation research in the last decades, studies of film title translations remain scant to this day (Peña-Cervel 2016: 307). Previous film title translation research can be divided into the Asian, primarily Chinese, and European geographical and cultural circles. Asian studies have mostly been interested in translation strategies of domestication and foreignisation (Yin 2009; Shi 2014; Mei 2010), while transliteration has been specifically addressed due to different writing systems used in the dominant source market, the United States (Beier et al. 1994: 5) and target markets (Yin 2009: 171–2). European studies have been chiefly engaged in detecting the sources of difficulties during the translation process (Leonardi 2011; Limon 2012; Berdis 2013; Šidiškytė and Tamulaitienė 2013; Jutronic and Karabatić 2016; Surdyk and Urban 2016). Limon (2012: 1–2), as well as Surdyk and Urban (2016: 153), cite repeated criticism of film and television show title translations by viewers as expressed on internet fora and similar platforms as a reason for embarking on film title translation research.

Almost all studies of film title translation analysed one source and one target language. Only Šidiškytė and Tamulaitienė (2013) conducted a comparative analysis of the translation of English comedy and thriller titles into Lithuanian and Russian, but found no significant differences. The only diachronic analysis we encountered was Schubert's (2004), in which he detected significant diachronic changes in the translation strategy choice for German translations of English film titles. In his corpus containing titles from 1944 to 2002, Schubert noted a dramatic increase in the number of transcriptions, which have been the first strategy choice since the 1964-1973 decade, after being only modestly represented in the 1944-1953 decade. This change is interpreted as resulting from globalisation effects and the immense effect of English on German (Schubert 2004: 257). Schubert's 2004 study is also the only notable study involving German film title translations, while Jutronic and Karabatić (2016) remain the only study with Croatian film title translations. Jutronic and Karabatić (2016: 101–2) concluded in their study that the appellative effect serves as the primary motive during the process of title translation. Negro Alousque (2015) and Peña-Cervel (2016) conducted cognitive analyses of film title

translations. However, the methodology and interpretations in the studies seem somewhat controversial.

Methodologically, most studies have relied on a classification of translation strategies developed on the basis of different types of manipulation of lexical-semantic structures of the original title during the translation process. Schubert (2004) used the most detailed classification, which we used in our own analysis in a slightly modified form. Our modified classification includes the following translation strategies:

1. *Direct translation* [e.g. *The Sixth Sense* (1999) > Cr. *Šesto čulo*] is semantically similar to the original. A direct translation is a sign that the translator of the title did not encounter cultural and/or specific linguistic difficulties (Schubert 2004: 242). However, certain connotations have been known to get lost in a direct translation due to cultural and/or specific linguistic differences between the source and target languages. Schubert exemplifies this with the translation of the title *The Color of Money* (1986) into German (*Die Farbe des Geldes*) where the colour green marking the currency of the source market is invoked in the original title, but no such connections are elicited in the German translation. It is clear that the definition of direct translation is highly dependent on the particular semantic theory used in defining the concept. Direct translations were often not the focal point of film title translation studies, as most studies were preoccupied with the sources of difficulties in the translation process.
2. *Free translation* is a translation which has survived specific modifications, but has retained some semantic equivalence. Modifications taken into account in this study include addition, subtraction, substitution and shift.
 - a. *Addition* [e.g. *Dawn of the Dead* (2004) > Cr. *Zora živih mrtvaca* 'dawn of the living dead'] is an enlargement of the original title during the translation process by joining new lexical-semantic structures. Several studies analysing different languages noted that specific lexical-semantic structures were systematically included in additions such as

emotionally salient lexemes and proper nouns (Leonardi 2011: 14; Schubert 2004: 245).

- b. *Subtraction* [e.g. *Everything You Always Wanted to Know About Sex * But Were Afraid to Ask* (1972) > Cr. *Sve što ste željeli znati o seksu* 'everything you wanted to know about sex'] is a partial removal of lexical-semantic structures during the translation process. Studies have noted that at least some subtraction cases are encouraged by exceedingly long titles, such as *Who Is Harry Kellerman and Why Is He Saying Those Terrible Things About Me?* (1971), which was translated into German as *Wer ist Harry Kellerman?* 'who is Harry Kellerman' (Schubert 2004: 242–3).
- c. *Shift* [e.g. *To Catch a Thief* (1955) > *Uhvatite lopova* 'catch_{IMP 2. PL} the thief'] is defined as a change of morphosyntactic structures during the translation process (Schubert, 2004: 243; cf. Catford 1965: 76). Schubert (2004: 244) suggests that shifts in translations into German obscure the meaning of the title in some cases, thus enabling multiple interpretations, which presumably intensifies the appellative effect of the translation. However, his idea is arguable. Another observation was an increase in dynamics through the conversion of a nominal phrase into a verbal one, e.g. *Ferris Bueller's Day Off* (1986) > Ge. *Ferris macht blau* 'Ferris skips school'.
- d. *Substitution* [e.g. *House on Haunted Hill* (1959) > Cr. *Kuća straha* 'house of fear'] includes a swap of lexical-semantic structures while morphosyntactic relations to other structures of the title remain relatively intact. Since in our preliminary analysis we found that morphosyntactic structures often experience at least some change when undergoing substitution, substitution is here defined more loosely compared to other translation strategies and could therefore be easily understood as a combination of addition and subtraction. Studies have indicated that specific lexical-semantic structures take the role of substitutes, such as highly concrete and emotionally salient lexemes

which, as in addition, supposedly reinforce the appellative effect (Schubert 2004: 243).

3. *Transcreation* [e.g. *American Beauty* (1999) > Cr. *Vrtlog života* 'vortex of life'] is a complete replacement of lexical-semantic structures during the translation process, which results in zero linguistic equivalence. Translation research has differentiated between obligatory and optional transcreations, depending on potential cultural and/or linguistic difficulties during the translation process (Limon 2012: 6; Schubert 2004: 246). Problematic cases include idiomatic expressions and titles with multiple possible interpretations. Studies analysing Slovenian and German title translations have interpreted transcreation as, among other, a means of explication (Limon 2012: 4; Schubert 2004: 246–8). Limon concluded in his study that 41.3% of free translations and transcreations in his corpus included changes in the original title for the purposes of explication in order to more clearly convey the genre of the film and thus to target the appropriate audience. Schubert has suggested that a great deal of German transcretions show a tendency for personalisation, e.g. *First Blood* (1982) > Ge. *Rambo* 'proper name', or include emotionally salient lexemes. It is a general agreement that transcreations are mainly due to intentions of enhancing the appellative effect (Surdyk and Urban 2016: 168).
4. *Transcription* – Transcription is a strategy whereby exact lexical-semantic structures from the original title are retained, with possible modifications. Jutronić and Karabatić (2015: 87) found a considerable amount of transcriptions in their analysis of Croatian translations and linked this phenomenon to the high degree of prestige that English has among Croatian speakers.
 - a. *Complete transcription* [e.g. *Spider-Man* (2002) > Cr. *Spider-Man* 'proper name'] indicates the identity in expression between the original title and the translation. Studies have shown that this is often the case with original titles consisting of only proper nouns (Schubert 2004: 251–3). However, complete transcriptions have been known to lose phonetic associations, as is the case in *Major Payne* (1995), which was

transcribed into Slovenian, thus eliminating the association caused by the homophonic expressions *Payne* and *pain*, both [peɪn] (Limon 2012: 2).

- b. *Additions* [e.g. *Octopussy* (1983) > Ge. *James Bond: Octopussy*] mostly include subheadings, as noted by Schubert (2004: 249-51). While some subheadings have the role of explication, some are “semantically relatively empty”¹. According to Schubert, such “nonsense titles” still deliver an increase to the appellative effect and are found first and foremost in mainstream comedies.
- c. *Subtraction* [e.g. *The Karate Kid* (1984) > Cr. *Karate Kid*] is rarely found among transcriptions (Schubert 2004: 251).
- d. *Substitution* [e.g. *Pirates of the Caribbean: Dead Man’s Chest* (2006) > *Pirates of the Caribbean – Fluch der Karibik 2* ‘curse of the Caribbean 2’] is equally rare (Ibid.).

During the analysis we established that some film title translations did not fit any of our proposed translation strategies. We were therefore compelled to expand our classification. The mixed type of free translation was added, characterised by two or more subtypes of modifications. Furthermore, combinations of translation, either direct or free, and transcription were detected, but remained quantitatively very limited and were consequently excluded from the qualitative analysis.

For the diagrams, please see Appendix 2.

4. Aims and hypotheses

The aim of this study was to analyse strategies employed in film title translation into Croatian and German and to discern specific strategies employed in the appellative effect transfer. This would allow us to detect valuable research points which could be pursued in future studies to increase our understanding of the film title translation process.

¹ “Semantisch relativ leer” (translated by the authors).

We hypothesised that the Croatian and German film title translations would show quantitative differences in the choice of translation strategies. We further hypothesised that diachronic changes would be detected in both subcorpora and that the two subcorpora would show some similarities in the change of diachronic patterns due to globalisation effects and that the patterns could be correlated with specific cultural-historical processes. In addition, we hypothesised that most of the recognised patterns in the analysis could be explained with the help of the appellative effect transfer.

5. Methodology

We manually created a corpus consisting of 935 original film titles in various languages and their 915 Croatian and 914 German translations. The full corpus is available in Appendix 1. We focused on a timeframe from 1923 and 2017. The selected timeframe was segmented into 10-year periods, enabling us to calculate the proportion of particular translation strategies for each period. For each year, 10 original film titles with the highest number of votes were included in the corpus. We used this criterion in order to analyse the appellative effect transfer, as we assumed that the number of votes would correlate with the number of viewings of a film. Not all film titles had both the Croatian and German translation. Furthermore, some original titles were already in German. There were no original titles in Croatian. Every title was translated into at least one of the analysed target languages. Original titles were mostly in English, as was the case in all studies dealing with film title translation we reviewed (Schubert 2004; Mei 2010; Leonardi 2011; Limon 2012; Berdis 2013; Šidiškytė and Tamulaitienė 2013; Negro Alousque 2015; Jutronić and Karabatić 2016; Surdyk and Urban 2016; Peña-Cervel 2016). Other source languages in our study include, in order of frequency, French (30), Italian (15), German (15), Japanese (14), Russian (6), Swedish (4), Spanish (3), Latin (1), Korean (1), Portuguese (1) and Danish (1). Original titles were obtained from the website IMDb (Internet Movie Database; *imdb.com*), an online database offering

relevant information on films, television shows and video games². IMDb was used in corpus building by other relevant studies as well (Schubert 2004; Berdis 2013; Surdyk and Urban 2016; Peña-Cervel 2016).

Most title translations into Croatian were gathered from the online edition of the *Film Lexicon (Filmski leksikon; Kragić and Gilić 2003)* published by the Miroslav Krleža Institute of Lexicography (*film.lzmk.hr*) and the websites *filmski.net*, *mojtv.hr*, *moj-film.hr* and *blitz-cinestar.hr*. Two of these websites, *mojtv.hr* and *moj-film.hr*, were used by Jutronic and Karabatic (2016) in their study as well. Translations into German were retrieved from the websites *moviepilot.de* and *cineplex.de*. In some cases, during our preliminary analysis, we encountered German translations specific for the Swiss and Austrian markets. These title translations were excluded from the analysis. We were presented with a similar situation in the Croatian subcorpus where we came upon Croatian translations specific for the Bosnian market. These translations were excluded as well. Thus we could focus specifically on the Croatian and German markets.

The first step in the corpus analysis was to classify the film title translations according to specific strategies found in our classification presented earlier (Section 3). The data was quantitatively and qualitatively analysed for each target language separately and then compared.

In our diachronic analysis, we calculated the proportion of particular translation strategies for each 10-year period from 1923 to 2017. Since we wanted to offer a preliminary explanation for potential diachronic changes, we compared the temporal perspective of some diachronic changes with the timeline of relevant cultural-historical processes that presumably had global influence. Special attention was given to processes occurring in the American film industry, or Hollywood, as that was the source of most of the analysed film titles. Hollywood became a notable place in the global film industry during and immediately after World War II. At this time the European film industry came to a halt, enabling Hollywood's domination of the industry. However, at the end of the 1950s and the beginning of the 1960s,

² Surdyk and Urban (2016: 157) describe IMDb as "the world's most popular and authoritative source for movie, TV and celebrity content".

Hollywood entered a period of stagnation (Peterlić 1986: 557). During that time there was also a reduction in the number of cinemas in Germany (Lorenzo 2015: 109). From the 1960s to the 1980s the so-called era of New Hollywood began, characterised by the strengthening of the director's artistic role; at the same time the major film studios engaged primarily in film distribution and global marketing (Peterlić 1986: 535). A distinction is made between early New Hollywood, also called Hollywood Renaissance, which ended in the second half of the 1970s, and the Late New Hollywood (Kokonis 2008: 171). In the 1990s multiplex cinemas came to the forefront, which shifted the focus to massive film projections through which the number of cinema goers drastically increased, both in the US and in Germany (Lorenzo 2015: 110).

6. Results and discussion

6.1 Comparative analysis

In most cases (60.1%) film titles were directly translated into Croatian. Direct translation was followed by free translation (17%) and transcription (15.5%). Transcreation was represented by 6.7% of the title translations, while combinations of a translation and transcription were scarce (0.8%). Film titles were chiefly transcribed into German (39.7%), while direct translation was also considerably represented (25.4%). These were followed relatively closely by transcreation (17%) and free translation (16.8%). Combinations of a translation and transcription were, similarly to the Croatian subcorpus, limited to 1%.

6.1.1 Direct translation

Direct translation was considerably more represented in the Croatian subcorpus than in the German one. Some original titles in our corpora were directly translated although there were clear cultural and/or linguistic difficulties in the translation process. For example, the film title *V for Vendetta* (2005) was directly translated into Croatian as *O za osvetu* even though the grapheme *V* is a relevant visual motive in the film. Furthermore, we observed direct translations that were identical to the

translation of a literary title on which the plot of the film was based, e.g. *War of the Worlds* (2005) > *Rat svjetova*. However, it is difficult to assess whether the title was translated anew or if the previous translation of a literary title was adopted. Nevertheless, it could be presumed that the adoption of an already existing translation could add to the appellative effect of the translation through the serial effect, which is “the consumer’s belief that new products from the same group have a constantly high quality”³ (Schubert 2004: 247).

6.1.2 Free translation

Free translation as a whole was present in similar proportions in both subcorpora. Croatian free translations were led by shifts (29.9%), which were closely followed by substitutions (26.8%) and additions (21.7%). Subtraction and the mixed type appeared in slightly lower proportions, 13.4% and 8.3% respectively. German translations were dominated by substitutions (36.4%), which were followed by shifts (18.8%), subtractions (17.5%), additions (16.2%) and the mixed type (11%). Subtle differences between the two markets are observable.

When it comes to additions, there were some differences between the two subcorpora. A closer look at additions in the Croatian subcorpus reveals that in most cases the motivation for additions can be discerned. In 32.4% of the cases there is a tendency of enhancing the serial effect by adding lexical-semantic structures indicating that the film is part of a series, e.g. *The Man with the Golden Gun* (1974) > Cr. *James Bond 007: Čovjek sa zlatnim pištoljem*. Interestingly, most of the serial markers include character names. Addition seems also to have served as a means of explication, at least in 23.5% cases, e.g. *Airplane!* (1980) > Cr. *Ima li pilota u avionu* ‘is there a pilot on the plane’. Sometimes keywords for the explication of a genre were also involved, *Dawn of the Dead* (1978) > Cr. *Zora živih mrtvaca* ‘dawn of the living dead’. The addition of emotionally salient lexemes was discovered in only four cases (11.8%) and included in two instances the abstract lexeme DEATH, a diminutive and an attribute. As was the case with the Croatian subcorpus, German

³ “Dem Glauben der Konsument(inn)en, dass neue Produkte aus derselben Gruppe eine konstant hohe Qualität aufweisen” (translated by the authors).

additions had the role of creating the serial effect (in 37.5% of the cases), e.g. *Sons of the Desert* (1933) > Ge. *Laurel und Hardy: Die Wüstensöhne* 'Laurel and Hardy: the desert sons'. The proportion of emotionally salient lexemes was somewhat higher in the German subcorpus, with 25% of the translations which were mostly expanded with the use of attributes. In four cases (16.7%) character names were introduced to the title, without having the purpose of achieving the serial effect, e.g. *The Martian* (2015) > Ge. *Der Marsianer – Rettet Mark Watney* 'the Martian – save Mark Watney'. There were no such cases in the Croatian subcorpus.

Regarding addition, we also observed that in both subcorpora most additions include series markers and, interestingly, their proportions are comparable. This suggests that original titles of films belonging to a series which are not marked as such are similarly treated both in Croatia and in Germany. Contrary to these similar trends in the process of marking the affiliation to a series, there were no cases of explication in the German subcorpus, while this motivation was highly represented in the Croatian subcorpus. Moderate differences were present in the proportions of emotionally salient lexemes, the higher proportion being found in the German subcorpus. Personalisation was modestly present only in the German subcorpus. Although it is difficult to judge which of the motivations would produce a greater appellative effect, these results possibly suggest that the orientation towards a more powerful appellative effect was more present during the translation process into German than into Croatian.

Subtraction was present in similar proportions in both subcorpora. In the Croatian subcorpus, 38.1% of the subtractions excluded a redundant series marker. In all of these cases, original titles include either the marker *part* or *episode* (which incidentally only appears in titles of the *Star Wars* film series). One example is *The Hangover Part II* (2011) > *Mamurluk 2* 'hangover 2'. Subtraction resulting from the shortening of an exceedingly long title was also present in 38.1% of the cases. In most cases (75%) the subheading was lost, e.g. *The Naked Gun: From the Files of Police Squad!* (1988) > *Goli pištolj* 'naked gun'. In the German subcorpus, the shortening of an exceedingly long title was present in 25.9% of the cases, e.g. *The Lodger: A Story of the London Fog* (1927) > *Der Mieter* 'the lodger'. There were

some cases (14.8%) of a redundant marker exclusion, e.g. *The Godfather: Part III* (1990) > *Der Pate 3* 'the godfather 3'. Apart from a single case when an already existing literary title translation was adopted, motivations for all other subtractions in the German subcorpus remain unclear. While the obvious trend in the Croatian subcorpus was to shorten long original titles, possibly to allow greater clarity, the percentage of shortening was considerably lower in the German subcorpus.

The proportions of shifts show moderate differences between the two subcorpora. What is perhaps more notable is that shifts and substitutions appear in similar proportions in the Croatian subcorpus, while their proportions are rather different in the German subcorpus, where substitutions are favoured over shifts. Initially one might assume that a higher proportion of shifts in the Croatian subcorpus can be explained by greater morphosyntactic differences between Croatian and English as the prevailing source text, as opposed to German and English. However, a closer look shows that only 12.8% of the shifts in the Croatian subcorpus can be interpreted as interventions due to morphosyntactic differences between the source languages and Croatian, e.g. *He Who Gets Slapped* (1924) > *Onaj kojega su tresnuli* 'the one who they slapped', where the passive construction was hard to transmit. There were three cases (6.3%) of salient emotional connotations resulting from a shift. For example, in *The Thin Man* (1934) > *Mršavko* 'thin-suffix', instead of a lexeme equivalent to MAN, the suffix *-ko* is inserted which nominalises the adjective, denotes a person and functions as a hypocoristic (Barić et al., 2005: 329). Only two cases (4.2%) of explication were detected, e.g. *Roman Holiday* (1953) > *Praznik u Rimu* 'holiday in Rome'. Remarkably, motivation in other cases remains enigmatic. In the German subcorpus, 20.7% of the shifts were due to morphosyntactic differences between the languages, e.g. *Edward Scissorhands* (1990) > *Edward mit den Scherenhänden* 'Edward with the scissor hands'. Yet other cases of shifts continue to be unclear. Although for reasons of linguistic typology one might expect a higher proportion of shifts in the Croatian subcorpus than in the German one, they are actually similar and slightly more substantial in the German subcorpus. It would appear that, when encountering difficulties due to the morphosyntactic differences between the source and target languages, translation strategies other than shifts are implemented in the translation process. Although the

proportion of explication was very low in the Croatian subcorpus, it seems rather indicative that there were yet again no explication cases in the German subcorpus.

Substitutions were moderately more numerous in the German subcorpus compared to the Croatian one. Once again most changes were made with unclear motivation. Both explication and interventions due to linguistic differences were modestly present at 14.3% in the Croatian subcorpus. An example with a clear difficulty was the original title *(500) Days of Summer* (2009) which was translated into Croatian as *(500) dana ljubavi* '(500) days of love'. The difficulty was caused by the homonymy between the English lexeme SUMMER and the character name *Summer*, which was impossible to convey in the translation. Five cases (11.9%) included emotionally salient lexemes as substitutes, e.g. *Ace Ventura: Pet Detective* (1994) > *Ace Ventura: Šašavi detektiv* 'Ace Ventura: the wacky detective'. Most other cases of substitution remain vaguely motivated. Substitution was the most common subtype of the free translation strategy in the German subcorpus. Although motivation is unclear in most cases, first explication cases were detected in the German subcorpus, but they were present in only 9.1% cases. Substitutes in most interpretable cases were emotionally salient lexemes (23.6%), e.g. *Our Hospitality* (1923) > *Verflixte Gastfreundschaft* 'darned hospitality'. Clear differences are noticeable between the two subcorpora. While in the Croatian subcorpus substitution had a role in the translinguistic reconciliation, no such aspect was detected in the German subcorpus. Yet again there were moderate differences in the proportion of emotional connotations, which were more substantial in the German subcorpus.

Free translation of the mixed type was modestly represented in both subcorpora. No systematic data was found in the analysis regarding free translation of the mixed type.

6.1.3 Transcreation

The proportion of transcreation showed mild differences between the two subcorpora, with the German subcorpus containing more instances of this strategy. In the Croatian subcorpus, 21.3% of the transcreations facilitated explication, e.g. *Now You See Me* (2013) > *Majstori iluzije* 'masters of illusion'. In 13.1% of the cases

emotionally salient lexemes were added during the transcreation process. Most other cases are without a clear interpretation. In the German subcorpus, a large number of transcreations did not have a clear interpretation either. In 9.3% of the cases an emotional connotation was introduced. In most of the cases the lexemes served for the explication of the genre, for example in *White Heat* (1949) > *Sprung in den Tod* 'the jump into death' where the translation suggests a thriller. In 7.4% of the cases a proper noun was inserted during the transcreation process, e.g. *The Most Dangerous Game* (1932) > *Graf Zaroff – Genie des Bösen* 'count Zaroff – genius of evil'. There were few cases of explication in the German subcorpus, making the proportion of such interventions in the Croatian subcorpus noticeably higher than in the German one. The proportion of lexemes with salient emotional connotations was similar in both subcorpora.

6.1.4 Transcription

There were pronounced differences in the proportion of transcription between the two subcorpora. While transcription was only modestly represented in the Croatian subcorpus, it was the primary choice in the German one. Croatian transcription was dominated by complete transcription (88.1%), which was followed by subtraction (9.8%) and addition (2.1%). The latter strategy was represented by only three cases in the entire subcorpus. German transcription was also led by complete transcription (69.3%), but included considerably more additions, which took the second position (24.3%). Subtraction was found in 5% of the cases. In the German subcorpus, substitutions were found in only four cases, and there was a single shift. Considerable differences are, therefore, noticeable in the proportions of complete transcription and addition between the two subcorpora. The fact that the German subcorpus contained substitutions and a shift, which were not represented in the Croatian subcorpus, and the fact that most original titles from the corpus were in English, suggests that English lexical-semantic structures are more acceptable when translating into German than into Croatian. However, the proportion of both translation strategies remain very low, calling for further arguments for this kind of interpretation.

The proportion of complete transcriptions was significantly higher in the Croatian subcorpus compared to the German one. Most complete transcriptions in the Croatian subcorpus were transcriptions of proper nouns (83.3%), e.g. *Mary Poppins* (1964). In 13.3% of the cases proper nouns included compound proper nouns such as *Iron Man* or *Spider-Man*. There were six cases (4.8%) of transcription in which there were either no clear lexical-semantic structures, e.g. *THX 1138* (1971), or the source language was ambiguous, e.g. *Ex Machina* (2015). There was one case of number transcription (0.8%), namely *300* (2006). Other cases of transcription have no clear motivation, but were quantitatively marginal. Contrary to the high proportion of clearly motivated complete transcriptions in the Croatian subcorpus, only 29.6% of the complete transcriptions in the German subcorpus are transcriptions of proper nouns. Cases similar to and including *THX 1138* and *Ex Machina* were found to constitute 2.4%. The same case of number transcription was also found in the German subcorpus. Therefore, while 88.9% of the complete transcriptions in the Croatian subcorpus are clearly motivated, only 32.4% of the complete transcriptions in the German subcorpus fall into that category.

There were considerably more additions in the German subcorpus compared to the Croatian one, in which only three cases of such interventions were found. Two of these included serial markers, e.g. *Octopussy* (1973) > *James Bond: Octopussy*. Almost all cases of addition in the German subcorpus involved the insertion of subheadings (94.3%), with only five titles remaining without a subheading. In 28.4% of the cases, additions involved lexemes with salient emotional connotations. As many as 68% of these cases had the purpose of genre explication, e.g. *Halloween II* (1981) > *Halloween II – Das Grauen kehrt zurück* ‘Halloween II – the horror returns’. Although a preliminary visual examination suggests that most of the subheaded transcriptions are nonsense subheadings, one group that stands out is comprised of combinations of a complete transcription and a direct translation. Eleven such cases (12.5%) were found, e.g. *The King’s Speech* (2010) > *The King’s Speech – Die Rede des Königs* ‘the king’s speech – the speech of the king’. There were limited amounts of explication and cases where series markers were used.

Subtraction was found in similar proportions in both subcorpora. However, depending on the theoretical classification one wishes to pursue, it would seem appropriate to count a large proportion of subtractions in both subcorpora as complete transcriptions. In the German subcorpus, for instance, 77.8% of the cases are exclusions of the initial definite article, e.g. *The Karate Kid* (1984) > *Karate Kid*. This was the case in 57.1% of the cases in the Croatian subcorpus. Additionally there were three cases (21.4%) of the exclusion of subheadings and three cases of the exclusion of redundant series markers in the Croatian subcorpus. In the German subcorpus, beside the initial definite article exclusion, in one case a subheading was excluded and in another a redundant series marker. Two cases had no clear motivation, e.g. *Silver Linings Playbook* (2012) > *Silver Linings*.

Substitutions and shifts were not found in the Croatian subcorpus, as already mentioned above. Four of the five cases in the German subcorpus include titles of films belonging to a series, the earliest being from 2006. The remaining translation is a fairly peculiar case of substitution: *The Addams Family* (1991) > *Die Addams Family* 'the Addams family'.

Translations in the German subcorpus systematically show lower proportions of explication compared to the Croatian subcorpus. Conversely, proportions of emotionally salient lexemes were higher in essentially all translation strategies investigated in our study. What is more, motivation for most modifications, when it comes to both free translation and transcription, was unclear in considerably more cases in the German subcorpus than was the case in the Croatian one. All this, along with the observed considerable differences in the diversity of transcriptions, suggests that the process of translation into German was much more modulated by the appellative effect transfer and increase, also allowing more room for the original appellative effect of English lexical-semantic structures. Because there were substantially more cases of explication and fewer cases of unmotivated transcreation and transcription in the Croatian subcorpus, clarity of title translation seems to be the central motivation in most cases. This interpretation is also supported by the fact that nonsense title transcriptions or nonsense subheadings were hard to find in the Croatian subcorpus, while they were abundant in the German one.

6.2 *Diachronic analysis*

In the first examined decade, between 1928 and 1937, the Croatian subcorpus was greatly dominated by direct translations (78.5%). Free translation and transcription appeared in much lower proportions (8.6% and 7.5% respectively). Transcreation and combinations of a translation and transcription (CTT) show marginal results. For the next several decades, moderate or in some cases slight fluctuations in the proportions of direct translation, free translation and transcription can be observed. Transcreation remained peripheral while CTTs were non-existent until 2006. In the 1978-1987 decade, a pronounced drop in direct translation was observed, from 73.7% in the previous decade to 49%. Comparing those two decades, we further found a substantial increase in free translation, from 6.3% to 22.4%, and a moderate increase in transcription, from 15.8% to 21.4%. Most of the transcriptions from this decade involved proper nouns, which suggests that this increase is mostly or solely due to sampling bias. Free translations, however, do not show any clear cause from the translator's point of view, as there were virtually no interventions due to linguistic differences between the source languages and Croatian. In the next decades no significant diachronic changes were detected. Free translation retained a higher proportion, constantly around 20%. Direct translation remained steady (around 50%). Transcription regularly constituted 20% after the end of the 1988-1997 decade. Transcreation gradually increased after the 1948-1957 decade to a modest proportion, regularly just below 10%. Diachronically, the most substantial changes were found in the proportion of direct translation, which dropped around 30% from the onset of our timeline. This was mostly picked up by free translation, which showed a moderate increase at one point and has remained at a similar level until present. Transcription recorded a moderate increase compared to the first decade, but the fluctuations observable from the second decade already showed values similar to the present ones. This led to the final decade still being dominated by direct translation (46.5%), followed by transcription (21.8%), free translation (18.8%), transcreation (8.9%) and CTTs (4%).

In the first examined decade, between 1928 and 1937, direct translation was the first strategy choice in the German subcorpus, with 44.4%. Other translation

strategies shared similar proportions: transcreation 21.1%, transcription 17.8% and free translation 16.7%. The next two decades showed mild increases in transcreation and free translation, combined with a moderate decrease in direct translation. In the 1958-1967 decade, fluctuations are apparent in all strategies, while transcription recorded its first moderate increase. This increase gradually gained ground and exploded in the 1978-1987 decade, when transcription became the first choice translation strategy, making up 54.7% of the cases. Consequently, all other translation strategies recorded moderate or substantial drops. Direct translation went from 40.6% in the 1958-1967 decade to 16.2% in the following decade. The trends have continued with limited fluctuations until today, when transcription is the predominant strategy (75.2%), followed by direct translation (8.9%), free translation (7.9%), transcreation (5.9%) and CTT (2%). The last decade recorded only a moderate decline in free translation.

Diachronic differences and similarities can be observed between the two subcorpora. In both subcorpora we observed prominent decreases in direct translation. In the Croatian subcorpus, there was a pronounced drop in the 1978-1987 decade, while the German subcorpus recorded a similar drop in the 1958-1967 decade and a subsequent gradual decline in the periods approaching the last decade. It is, however, not clear why the observed change showed different temporal values. The gradual decline was probably a consequence of a steady rise in transcription. What is more, a similar gradual decline was recorded in free translation and transcreation as well. In the Croatian subcorpus, moderate changes were observed with regard to free translation, which does not seem to be a product of sampling bias.

Although not many major diachronic changes were detected in our analysis, we can still make some connections to specific cultural-historical processes. According to the general timeline presented in Section 5, the major decline in direct translation observable in the German subcorpus seems to correlate with the onset of New Hollywood, which was characterised by a shift in the focus of major film studios from the artistic control of the movie production to the distribution of the film and its success on the global market. That is also the time when fluctuations in all

translation strategies appear in the German subcorpus, suggesting that cultural-historical changes influenced the process of film title translation. It also possibly suggests that there was a period of adjustment, since steady proportions of particular translation strategies emerged only later. However, sampling bias should be taken as a possibly influential factor. The explosion of transcription in the 1978-1987 decade can be correlated to advances in Hollywood's power during the later phases of New Hollywood. However, causal links remain unclear, probably due to the quite general outline of cultural-historical processes we used in our analysis. In the same decade that transcription ballooned in the German subcorpus, the Croatian subcorpus experienced a substantial decrease in direct translation and a moderate increase in free translation. These results imply that there were notable connections between cultural-historical processes in the 1980s, and possibly sooner, and diachronic changes in film title translation. Because film title translators are more focused on the appellative effect at present, it is possible that free translation and transcription, in the Croatian and German subcorpora respectively, were those translation strategies that were mostly associated with the appellative effect transfer.

7. Conclusion

The analysis of our corpus consisting of 935 film titles between 1923 and 2017 and their translations into Croatian and German yielded considerable quantitative and qualitative differences in translation strategy choices and their motivation between the two subcorpora. The most notable differences have to do with the proportion of direct translation, which was lower in the German subcorpus from the start of our timeline, but further experienced substantial drops, and which was not as pronounced in the Croatian subcorpus. Differences in diachronic patterns were observed as well, but clear interpretations of temporal differences are more difficult to make. Almost all non-direct translation strategies were characterised as increasing or maintaining the appellative effect of the title. Furthermore, correlations with specific cultural-historical processes, although extremely general, were observed. Sampling bias was a serious threat to our proposed interpretation. We

conclude that further research with bigger samples is needed to clarify the diachronic perspective.

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A COMPARATIVE AND DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF FILM TITLE TRANSLATIONS AND APPELLATIVE EFFECT TRANSFER INTO CROATIAN AND GERMAN

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Abstract

Studies of film title translations remain scant to this day. The existing studies mainly focus on investigating the sources of difficulties during the translation process. Although the studies employ different analytical approaches, the conclusion in almost all investigations is that the decisive objective during the translation process is the transfer or production of the appellative effect. This study investigates which strategies are employed during translation into Croatian and German and why, as well as possible diachronic changes in the choice of translation strategies. We created a corpus of 935 film titles from 1923 to 2017 and their translations into Croatian and German, which we first classified as direct translation, free translation, transcreation or transcription, and finally we quantitatively and qualitatively analysed the data. Our results show considerable differences between the two subcorpora in the choice of translation strategies and motivation, as well as in the patterns of diachronic change. Furthermore, correlations with specific cultural-historical processes are observed.

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Sažetak

Istraživanja o filmskim naslovima relativno su rijetka. Postojeća istraživanja bave se prvenstveno izvorima poteškoća u prijevodu. Iako se u tim istraživanjima koriste različiti analitički pristupi, zaključak je u gotovo svim slučajevima da je glavni cilj tijekom procesa prevođenja prijenos ili produkcija apelativnog efekta. U ovoj se studiji istražuje koje se strategije koriste tijekom prijevoda na hrvatski i njemački jezik te zašto. Također se istražuju i moguće dijakronijske promjene u izboru prijevodnih strategija. Sastavili smo korpus od naslova 935 filmova snimljenih od 1923. do 2017. te njihovih prijevoda na hrvatski i njemački jezik. Te smo naslove razvrstali u sljedeće kategorije: izravni prijevodi, slobodni prijevodi, transkreacije i transkripcije. Na kraju smo kvantitativno i kvalitativno analizirali podatke. Rezultati naše studije pokazuju značajne razlike između dvaju potkorpusa u izboru prijevodnih strategija i motivaciji te u obrascima dijakronijskih promjena. Nadalje smo opazili i korelacije s određenim kulturno-povijesnim procesima.

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Zusammenfassung

Studien von Filmtitelübersetzungen sind nach wie vor schwer zu finden. Die bisherigen Studien richteten sich vor allem auf die Untersuchung von Schwierigkeiten beim Übersetzungsprozess. Obwohl die Studien verschiedene analytische Vorgehensweisen in Anspruch nahmen, ist die Schlussfolgerung fast aller Untersuchungen, dass der Transfer oder die Produktion des appellativen Effektes das Ziel der Filmtitelübersetzung ist. Diese Studie untersucht, welche Strategien bei der Übersetzung ins Kroatische und Deutsche eingesetzt wurden und warum genau diese; dazu auch mögliche diachronische Veränderungen bei der Wahl der Übersetzungsstrategie.

Wir stellten ein Korpus von 935 Filmtiteln von 1923 bis 2017 und ihren Übersetzungen ins Kroatische und Deutsche zusammen. Die Übersetzungen wurden zunächst eingeordnet, und zwar als direkte Übersetzungen, freie Übersetzungen, Umtitelungen und Transkriptionen. Schließlich haben wir die Daten quantitativ und qualitativ analysiert. Unsere Ergebnisse zeigen bedeutende Unterschiede zwischen den zwei Subkorpora in der Wahl der Übersetzungsstrategie und Motivation, sowie in den Mustern der diachronischen Veränderungen. Weiterhin wurden Korrelationen zu spezifischen kulturell-historischen Prozessen festgestellt.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

1. Croatian subcorpus

1.1 Direct translations

La souriante Madame Beudet	1923	Nasmiješena gospođa Beudet
Our Hospitality	1923	Naše gostoprimstvo
The Pilgrim	1923	Hodočasnik
The Ten Commandments	1923	Deset zapovijedi
Entr'acte	1924	Međučin
Greed	1924	Pohlepa
The Navigator	1924	Navigator
The Thief of Bagdad	1924	Bagdadski lopov
Der letzte Mann	1924	Posljednji čovjek

Die Nibelungen: Kriemhilds Rache	1924	Nibelunzi: Kriemhildina osveta
The Gold Rush	1925	Potjera za zlatom
The Big Parade	1925	Velika parada
The Freshman	1925	Brucoš
Bronenosets Potyomkin	1925	Krstarica Potemkin
Stachka	1925	Štrajk
The Phantom of the Opera	1925	Fantom opere
The Lost World	1925	Izgubljeni svijet
Mat	1926	Mati
Die Abenteuer des Prinzen Achmeds	1926	Avanture princa Ahmeda
The General	1926	General
The Son of the Sheik	1926	Šeikov sin
Flesh and the Devil	1926	Put i đavao
Wings	1927	Krila
College	1927	Koledž
Berlin: Die Sinfonie der Grosstadt	1927	Berlin, simfonija velegrada
The Kid Brother	1927	Mlađi brat
The Lodger: A Story of the London Fog	1927	Stanar: Priča o londonskoj magli
The Jazz Singer	1927	Pjevač jazza
The Circus	1928	Cirkus
The Cameraman	1928	Kameraman
The Crowd	1928	Gomila
Oktyabr	1928	Oktobar
Steamboat Willie	1928	Parobrod Willy
The Man Who Laughs	1928	Čovjek koji se smije
Un chien andalou	1929	Andaluzijski pas
Blackmail	1929	Ucjena
The Broadway Melody	1929	Brodvejska melodija
Queen Kelly	1929	Kraljica Kelly
Big Business	1929	Veliki posao
Chelovek s kino-apparatom	1929	Čovjek s filmskom kamerom
Die Büchse der Pandora	1929	Pandorina kutija

Tagebuch einer Verlorenen	1929	Dnevnik izgubljene
L'âge d'or	1930	Zlatno doba
À propos de Nice	1930	Povodom Nice
Murder!	1930	Umorstvo
The Big Trail	1930	Veliki put
Morocco	1930	Maroko
Zemlya	1930	Zemlja
Der blaue Engel	1930	Plavi anđeo
City Lights	1931	Svjetla velegrada
The Public Enemy	1931	Državni neprijatelj
Monkey Business	1931	Majmunaska posla
Little Caesar	1931	Mali Cezar
Dracula	1931	Drakula
Freaks	1932	Nakaze
The Mummy	1932	Mumija
Trouble in Paradise	1932	Nevolje u raju
Horse Feathers	1932	Konjsko perje
Vampyr	1932	Vampir
Scarface	1932	Lice s ožiljkom
I Am a Fugitive from a Chain Gang	1932	Ja sam bjegunac iz Chain ganga
The Most Dangerous Game	1932	Najopasnija igra
Duck Soup	1933	Pačja juha
Sons of the Desert	1933	Sinovi pustinje
Queen Christina	1933	Kraljica Kristina
42nd Street	1933	Četrdeset i druga ulica
Das Testament des Dr. Mabuse	1933	Oporuka doktora Mabusea
The Invisible Man	1933	Nevidljivi čovjek
Dinner at Eight	1933	Večera u osam
It Happened One Night	1934	Dogodilo se jedne noći
The Man Who Knew Too Much	1934	Čovjek koji je previše znao
The Black Cat	1934	Crna mačka
The Gay Divorcee	1934	Vesela razvedenica

Twentieth Century	1934	Dvadeseto stoljeće
The Scarlet Empress	1934	Grimizna carica
Bride of Frankenstein	1935	Frankensteinova nevjesta
A Night at the Opera	1935	Noć u operi
Top Hat	1935	Cilindar
Triumph des Willens	1935	Trijumf volje
The 39 Steps	1935	39 stepenica
Mutiny on the Bounty	1935	Pobuna u Bountyju
Captain Blood	1935	Kapetan Blood
The Informer	1935	Potkazivač
A Tale of Two Cities	1935	Priča o dva grada
Anna Karenina	1935	Ana Karenjina
Modern Times	1936	Moderna vremena
My Man Godfrey	1936	Moj čovjek Godfrey
Mr. Deeds Goes to Town	1936	Gospodin Deeds ide u grad
Sabotage	1936	Sabotaža
The Petrified Forest	1936	Okamenjena šuma
Swing Time	1936	Doba swinga
Fury	1936	Bijes
Reefer Madness	1936	Ludilo trave
La grande illusion	1937	Velika iluzija
The Awful Truth	1937	Strašna istina
A Day at the Races	1937	Dan na utrkama
Young and Innocent	1937	Mladi i nevini
A Star Is Born	1937	Zvijezda je rođena
Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs	1937	Snjeguljica i sedam patuljaka
Lost Horizon	1937	Izgubljeni horizont
Stage Door	1937	Ulaz na pozornicu
Le quai des brumes	1938	Obala u magli
The Adventures of Robin Hood	1938	Pustolovine Robina Hooda
Holiday	1938	Praznik
Angels with Dirty Faces	1938	Anđeli garava lica

Mr. Smith Goes to Washington	1939	Gospodin Smith ide u Washington
Stagecoach	1939	Poštanska kočija
The Women	1939	Žene
The Roaring Twenties	1939	Burne dvadesete
Only Angels Have Wings	1939	Samo anđeli imaju krila
The Wizard of Oz	1939	Čarobnjak iz Oza
Wuthering Heights	1939	Orkanski visovi
The Great Dictator	1940	Veliki diktator
Fantasia	1940	Fantazija
The Philadelphia Story	1940	Philadelphijska priča
His Girl Friday	1940	Njegova djevojka Petko
The Shop Around the Corner	1940	Trgovina iza ugla
Foreign Correspondent	1940	Strani dopisnik
The Thief of Bagdad	1940	Bagdaski lopov
The Grapes of Wrath	1940	Plodovi gnjeva
Citizen Kane	1941	Građanin Kane
Suspicion	1941	Sumnja
The Maltese Falcon	1941	Malteški sokol
How Green Was My Valley	1941	Kako je bila zelena moja dolina
Sergeant York	1941	Narednik York
High Sierra	1941	Visoka Sierra
To Be or Not to Be	1942	Biti ili ne biti
Saboteur	1942	Saboter
Cat People	1942	Ljudi mačke
Mrs. Miniver	1942	Gospođa Miniver
The Magnificent Ambersons	1942	Veličanstveni Ambersonovi
Le corbeau	1943	Gavran
Shadow of a Doubt	1943	Sjenka sumnje
The Life and Death of Colonel Blimp	1943	Život i smrt pukovnika Blimpa
Heaven Can Wait	1943	Nebo može čekati
Vredens dag	1943	Dan gnjeva
For Whom the Bell Tolls	1943	Kome zvono zvoni

Sahara	1943	Sahara
Arsenic and Old Lace	1944	Arsen i stare čipke
Lifeboat	1944	Čamac za spašavanje
The Three Caballeros	1944	Tri kabaljerosa
To Have and Have Not	1944	Imati i nemati
The Woman in the Window	1944	Žena u izlogu
Les enfants du paradis	1945	Djeca raja
Brief Encounter	1945	Kratak susret
Roma città aperta	1945	Rim, otvoreni grad
Scarlet Street	1945	Grimizna ulica
The Lost Weekend	1945	Izgubljeni vikend
Detour	1945	Zaobilaznica
And Then There Were None	1945	I ne osta nijedan
The Picture of Dorian Gray	1945	Slika Dorijana Grayja
La belle et la bête	1946	Ljepotica i zvijer
Notorious	1946	Ozloglašena
The Best Years of Our Lives	1946	Najbolje godine našega života
My Darling Clementine	1946	Moja draga Klementina
The Big Sleep	1946	Duboki san
Great Expectations	1946	Velika iščekivanja
The Postman Always Rings Twice	1946	Poštar uvijek zvući dvaput
The Killers	1946	Ubojice
Monsieur Verdoux	1947	Gospodin Verdoux
Miracle on 34th Street	1947	Čudo u 34. ulici
Out of the Past	1947	Iz prošlosti
The Lady from Shanghai	1947	Dama iz Šangaja
The Paradine Case	1947	Slučaj Paradine
Black Narcissus	1947	Crni narcis
Dark Passage	1947	Mračni prolaz
The Ghost and Mrs. Muir	1947	Duh i gospođa Muir
Gentlemen's Agreement	1947	Đentlenski sporazum
The Bishop's Wife	1947	Biskupova žena

Rope	1948	Uže
The Naked City	1948	Goli grad
Ladri di biciclette	1948	Kradljivci bicikla
Red River	1948	Crvena rijeka
The Treasure of the Sierra Madre	1948	Blago Sierra Madre
The Heiress	1949	Nasljednica
The Third Man	1949	Treći čovjek
Adam's Rib	1949	Adamovo rebro
She Wore a Yellow Ribbon	1949	Nosila je žutu vrpcu
Nora inu	1949	Pas lotalica
All the King's Men	1949	Svi kraljevi ljudi
All About Eve	1950	Sve o Evi
Sunset Blvd.	1950	Bulevar sumraka
The Asphalt Jungle	1950	Džungla na asfaltu
In a Lonely Place	1950	Na osamljenom mjestu
Los ovidados	1950	Zaboravljeni
Cinderella	1950	Pepeljuga
The Day the Earth Stood Still	1951	Dan kad je zemlja stala
Ace in the Hole	1951	As u rukavu
A Place in the Sun	1951	Mjesto pod suncem
Alice in Wonderland	1951	Alisa u zemlji čudesa
A Streetcar Named Desire	1951	Tramvaj zvan čežnja
The African Queen	1951	Afrička kraljica
Jeux interdits	1952	Zabranjene igre
Limelight	1952	Svjetla pozornice
Monkey Business	1952	Majmunska posla
The Greatest Show on Earth	1952	Najveća predstava na svijetu
Ikiru	1952	Živjeti
High Noon	1952	Točno u podne
The Quiet Man	1952	Miran čovjek
Le salaire de la peur	1953	Nadnica za strah
The Big Heat	1953	Velika žega

Tôkyô monogatari	1953	Priča o Tokiju
Gentlemen Prefer Blondes	1953	Muškarci više vole plavuše
From Here to Eternity	1953	Odavde od vječnosti
The War of the Worlds	1953	Rat svjetova
Peter Pan	1953	Petar Pan
White Christmas	1954	Bijeli Božić
La strada	1954	Cesta
Shichinin no samurai	1954	Sedam samuraja
20,000 Leagues Under the Sea	1954	20 000 milja pod morem
Les diaboliques	1955	Demoni
Lady and the Tramp	1955	Dama i skitnica
Rebel Without a Cause	1955	Buntovnik bez razloga
The Night of the Hunter	1955	Noć lovca
East of Eden	1955	Istočno od raja
The Trouble with Harry	1955	Nevolje s Harryjem
The Ten Commandments	1956	Deset zapovijedi
The Man Who Knew Too Much	1956	Čovjek koji je previše znao
Forbidden Planet	1956	Zabranjen planet
The King and I	1956	Kralj i ja
The Searchers	1956	Tragači
Invasion of the Body Snatchers	1956	Invazija tjelokradica
Giant	1956	Div
Sweet Smell of Success	1957	Slatki miris uspjeha
Le notti di Cabiria	1957	Cabirijine noći
12 Angry Men	1957	12 gnjevnih ljudi
The Bridge on the River Kwai	1957	Most na rijeci Kwai
Paths of Glory	1957	Staze slave
Witness for the Prosecution	1957	Svjedok optužbe
Det sjunde inseglet	1957	Sedmi pečat
Mon oncle	1958	Moj ujak
Ascenseur pour l'échafaud	1958	Lift za gubilište
Touch of Evil	1958	Dodir zla

Cat on a Hot Tin Roof	1958	Mačka na vrućem limenom krovu
The Blob	1958	Gruda
Horror of Dracula	1958	Strava Dracule
Vertigo	1958	Vrtoglavica
The Fly	1958	Muha
Nort by Northwest	1959	Sjever-sjeverozapad
Anatomy of a Murder	1959	Anatomija jednog ubojstva
Some Like It Hot	1959	Neki to vole vruće
Les quatre cents coups	1959	400 udaraca
Hiroshima mon amour	1959	Hirošima, ljubavi moja
Plan 9 from Outer Space	1959	Plan 9 iz vanjskog svemira
Sleeping Beauty	1959	Trnoružica
The Apartment	1960	Apartment
The Time Machine	1960	Vremenski stroj
The Magnificent Seven	1960	Sedmorica veličanstvenih
À bout de souffle	1960	Do posljednjeg daha
La dolce vita	1960	Slatki život
Peeping Tom	1960	Voajer
Jungfrukällan	1960	Djevičanski izvor
Psycho	1960	Psiho
The Innocents	1961	Nevini
Breakfast at Tiffany's	1961	Doručak kod Tiffanyja
One Hundred and One Dalmatians	1961	101 Dalmatinac
The Guns of Navarone	1961	Topovi s Navaronea
Judgment at Nuremberg	1961	Suđenje u Nürnbergu
West Side Story	1961	Priča sa zapadne strane
Yôjinbô	1961	Tjelesna straža
The Hustler	1961	Hazarder
To Kill a Mockingbird	1962	Ubiti pticu rugalicu
The Manchurian Candidate	1962	Mandžurijski kandidat
The Man Who Shot Liberty Valance	1962	Čovjek koji je ubio Liberty Valancea
The Longest Day	1962	Najduži dan

What Ever Happened to Baby Jane?	1962	Što se dogodilo s Baby Jane?
Lawrence of Arabia	1962	Lawrence od Arabije
Jules et Jim	1962	Jules i Jim
La jetée	1962	Nasip
The Great Escape	1963	Veliki bijeg
From Russia with Love	1963	Iz Rusije s ljubavlju
The Birds	1963	Ptice
The Sword in the Stone	1963	Mač u kamenu
Charade	1963	Šarada
Otto e mezzo	1963	Osam i pol
Cleopatra	1963	Kleopatra
My Fair Lady	1964	Moja draga lady
Per un pugno di dollari	1964	Za šaku dolara
A Hard Day's Night	1964	Noć nakon teškog dana
Rudolph, the Red-Nosed Reindeer	1964	Rudolf, sob crvenog nosa
Pierrot le fou	1965	Ludi Pierrot
Alphaville, une étrange aventure de Lemmy Caution	1965	Alphaville, neobična avantura Lemmyja Cautiona
The Flight of the Phoenix	1965	Feniksov let
Repulsion	1965	Odvratnost
Per qualche dollaro in più	1965	Za dolar više
A Charlie Brown Christmas	1965	Božić Charlieja Browna
Help!	1965	U pomoć!
Doctor Zhivago	1965	Doktor Živago
Blowup	1966	Povećanje
Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?	1966	Tko se boji Virginije Woolf ?
How the Grinch Stole Christmas!	1966	Kako je Grinch ukrao Božić!
A Man for All Seasons	1966	Čovjek za sva vremena
Il buono, il brutto, il cattivo	1966	Dobar, loš, zao
La battaglia di Algeri	1966	Bitka za Alžir
The Graduate	1967	Diplomac
The Producers	1967	Producenti
In the Heat of the Night	1967	U vrelini noći

You Only Live Twice	1967	Samo dvaput se živi
Bonnie and Clyde	1967	Bonnie i Clyde
The Jungle Book	1967	Knjiga o džungli
2001: A Space Odyssey	1968	2001: Odiseja u svemiru
Night of the Living Dead	1968	Noć živih mrtvaca
Planet of the Apes	1968	Planet majmuna
Rosemary's Baby	1968	Rosemaryna beba
The Party	1968	Zabava
C'era una volta il West	1968	Bilo jednom na Divljem zapadu
The Wild Bunch	1969	Divlja horda
L'armée des ombres	1969	Vojska sjena
Take the Money and Run	1969	Uzmi novac i bježi
Battle of Britain	1969	Bitka za Britaniju
Midnight Cowboy	1969	Ponoćni kauboj
Butch Cassidy and the Sundance Kid	1969	Butch Cassidy i Sundance Kid
Beneath the Planet of the Apes	1970	Ispod planeta majmuna
Five Easy Pieces	1970	Pet lakih komada
Little Big Man	1970	Mali veliki čovjek
Love Story	1970	Ljubavna priča
Dirty Harry	1971	Prljavi Harry
Duel	1971	Dvoboj
The Last Picture Show	1971	Posljednja kino predstava
Harold and Maude	1971	Harold i Maude
Straw Dogs	1971	Psi od slame
The French Connection	1971	Francuska veza
The Godfather	1972	Kum
Deliverance	1972	Oslobađanje
Sleuth	1972	Njuškalo
The Poseidon Adventure	1972	Posejdonova avantura
Frenzy	1972	Mahnitost
Ultimo tango a Parigi	1972	Posljednji tango u Parizu
Aguirre, der Zorn Gottes	1972	Aguirre, gnjev božji

The Exorcist	1973	Istjerivač đavola
The Sting	1973	Žalac
American Graffiti	1973	Američki grafiti
The Wicker Man	1973	Čovjek od pruća
Papillon	1973	Leptir
Chinatown	1974	Kineska četvrt
Young Frankenstein	1974	Mladi Frankenstein
The Texas Chain Saw Massacre	1974	Teksaški masakr motornom pilom
Blazing Saddles	1974	Vruća sedla
Murder on the Orient Express	1974	Ubojstvo u Orient Expressu
Death Wish	1974	Smrtonosna želja
Jaws	1975	Ralje
Monty Python and the Holy Grail	1975	Monty Python i Sveti gral
Three Days of the Condor	1975	Tri dana Kondora
Sholay	1975	Oganj
Dog Day Afternoon	1975	Pasje poslijepodne
Salò o le 120 giornate di Sodoma	1975	Salò, ili 120 dana Sodome
Taxi Driver	1976	Taksist
Network	1976	TV mreža
The Omen	1976	Pretkazanje
All the President's Men	1976	Svi predsjednikovi ljudi
The Outlaw Josey Wales	1976	Odmetnik Josey Wales
Marathon Man	1976	Maratonac
Logan's Run	1976	Loganov bijeg
The Enforcer	1976	Istjerivač pravde
Close Encounters of the Third Kind	1977	Bliski susreti treće vrste
Saturday Night Fever	1977	Groznica subotnje večeri
The Rescuers	1977	Spasitelji
Smokey and the Bandit	1977	Smokey i Bandit
Star Wars	1977	Zvezdani ratovi
The Deer Hunter	1978	Lovac na jelene
Grease	1978	Briljantin

Halloween	1978	Noć vještica
Animal House	1978	Zvjerinjak
Midnight Express	1978	Ponoćni ekspres
Jaws 2	1978	Ralje 2
Invasion of the Body Snatchers	1978	Invazija tjelokradica
Kramer vs. Kramer	1979	Kramer protiv Kramera
Escape from Alcatraz	1979	Bijeg iz Alcatraza
The Shining	1980	Isijavanje
Raging Bull	1980	Razjareni bik
The Elephant Man	1980	Čovjek slon
The Blues Brothers	1980	Braća Blues
Friday the 13th	1980	Petak 13-ti
The Blue Lagoon	1980	Plava laguna
Escape from New York	1981	Bijeg iz New Yorka
An American Werewolf in London	1981	Američki vukodlak u Londonu
The Fox and the Hound	1981	Lisica i pas
Halloween II	1981	Noć vještica 2
Conan the Barbarian	1982	Konan Barbarin
The Thing	1982	Stvor
Scarface	1983	Lice s ožiljkom
A Christmas Story	1983	Božićna priča
WarGames	1983	Ratne igre
Videodrome	1983	Videodrom
Risky Business	1983	Riskantan posao
The Terminator	1984	Terminator
Ghostbusters	1984	Istjerivači duhova
A Nightmare on Elm Street	1984	Strava u ulici Brijestova
Gremlins	1984	Gremlini
Beverly Hills Cop	1984	Policajac s Beverly Hillsa
This Is Spinal Tap	1984	Ovo je Spinal Tap
Indiana Jones and the Temple of Doom	1984	Indiana Jones i ukleti hram
Back to the Future	1985	Povratak u budućnost

Commando	1985	Komandos
Brazil	1985	Brazil
Stand by Me	1986	Ostani uz mene
Ferris Bueller's Day Off	1986	Slobodan dan Ferrisa Buellera
Blue Velvet	1986	Plavi baršun
The Fly	1986	Muha
Highlander	1986	Gorštak
Labyrinth	1986	Labirint
The Princess Bride	1987	Kraljevena nevjesta
The Untouchables	1987	Nedodirljivi
Lethal Weapon	1987	Smrtonosno oružje
Dirty Dancing	1987	Prljavi ples
Spaceballs	1987	Svemirske lopte
Predator	1987	Predator
Rain Man	1988	Kišni čovjek
Who Framed Roger Rabbit	1988	Tko je smjestio zeki Rogeru?
Nuovo Cinema Paradiso	1988	Novo kino Raj
Tonari no Totoro	1988	Moj susjed Totoro
Hotaru no haka	1988	Groblje krijesnica
Indiana Jones and the Last Crusade	1989	Indiana Jones i Posljednji križarski pohod
Dead Poets Society	1989	Društvo mrtvih pjesnika
The Little Mermaid	1989	Mala sirena
When Harry Met Sally...	1989	Kad je Harry sreo Sally
Ghostbusters II	1989	Istjerivači duhova 2
The Abyss	1989	Bezdan
Lethal Weapon 2	1989	Smrtonosno oružje 2
Honey, I Shrunk the Kids	1989	Draga, smanjio sam djecu
Goodfellas	1990	Dobri momci
Edward Scissorhands	1990	Edward Škaroruki
Home Alone	1990	Sam u kući
Total Recall	1990	Totalni opoziv
Pretty Woman	1990	Zgodna žena

Ghost	1990	Duh
Terminator 2: Judgment Day	1991	Terminator 2: Sudnji dan
Thelma & Louise	1991	Thelma i Louise
Beauty and the Beast	1991	Ljepotica i zvijer
Robin Hood: Prince of Thieves	1991	Robin Hood: Princ lopova
The Addams Family	1991	Obitelj Adams
Reservoir Dogs	1992	Psi iz rezervoara
Batman Returns	1992	Batman se vraća
Scent of a Woman	1992	Miris žene
A Few Good Men	1992	Malo dobrih ljudi
Dracula	1992	Drakula
What's Eating Gilbert Grape	1993	Što muči Gilberta Grapea
Schindler's List	1993	Schindlerova lista
Jurassic Park	1993	Jurski park
The Fugitive	1993	Bjegunac
True Romance	1993	Prava romansa
Dumb & Dumber	1994	Glup i gluplji
The Mask	1994	Maska
Speed	1994	Brzina
The Shawshank Redemption	1994	Iskupljenje u Shawshanku
Braveheart	1995	Hrabro srce
Toy Story	1995	Priča o igračkama
Twelve Monkeys	1995	12 majmuna
Heat	1995	Vrućina
Casino	1995	Kasino
Se7en	1995	Sedam
Independence Day	1996	Dan nezavisnosti
The Rock	1996	Hrid
Scream	1996	Vrisak
From Dusk Till Dawn	1996	Od sumraka do zore
Mars Attacks!	1996	Mars napada
Good Will Hunting	1997	Dobri Will Hunting

L.A. Confidential	1997	L.A. povjerljivo
Le cinquième élément	1997	Peti element
The Game	1997	Igra
The Devil's Advocate	1997	Đavolji odvjetnik
La vita è bella	1997	Život je lijep
Saving Private Ryan	1998	Spašavanje vojnika Ryana
The Truman Show	1998	Trumanov šou
The Big Lebowski	1998	Veliki Lebowski
Fear and Loathing in Las Vegas	1998	Strah i prezir u Las Vegasu
The Green Mile	1999	Zelena milja
The Sixth Sense	1999	Šesto čulo
Star Wars: Episode I – The Phantom Menace	1999	Zvezdani ratovi Epizoda 1: Fantomska prijetnja
Toy Story 2	1999	Priča o igračkama 2
The Mummy	1999	Mumija
American Pie	1999	Američka pita
Sleepy Hollow	1999	Sanjiva dolina
Gladiator	2000	Gladijator
American Psycho	2000	Američki psiho
Le fabuleux destin d'Amélie Poulain	2001	Čudesna sudbina Amélie Poulain
Ocean's Eleven	2001	Oceanovih jedanaest
Training Day	2001	Dan obuke
The Lord of the Rings: The Fellowship of the Ring	2001	Gospodar prstenova: Prstenova družina
Catch Me If You Can	2002	Uhvati me ako možeš
The Pianist	2002	Pijanist
The Bourne Identity	2002	Bourneov identitet
Ice Age	2002	Ledeno doba
Cidade de Deus	2002	Božji grad
The Lord of the Rings: The Two Towers	2002	Gospodar prstenova: Dvije kule
Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets	2002	Harry Potter i Odaja tajni
Mystic River	2003	Mistična rijeka
Pirates of the Caribbean: The Curse of the Black Pearl	2003	Pirati s Kariba: Prokletstvo crnog bisera
Big Fish	2003	Krupna riba

The Lord of the Rings: The Return of the King	2003	Gospodar prstenova: Povratak kralja
Troy	2004	Troja
I, Robot	2004	Ja, robot
Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban	2004	Harry Potter i Zatočenik Azkabana
Star Wars: Episode III – Revenge of the Sith	2005	Ratovi zvijezda: Epizoda III – Osveta Sitha
Mr. & Mrs. Smith	2005	Gospodin i gospođa Smith
War of the Worlds	2005	Rat svjetova
Charlie and the Chocolate Factory	2005	Charlie i tvornica čokolade
V for Vendetta	2005	O za osvetu
Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire	2005	Harry Potter i Plameni pehar
The Departed	2006	Pokojni
Pirates of the Caribbean: Dead Man's Chest	2006	Pirati s Kariba: Mrtvačeva škrinja
Blood Diamond	2006	Krvavi dijamant
The Prestige	2006	Prestiž
El laberinto del fauno	2006	Panov labirint
I Am Legend	2007	Ja sam legenda
Transformers	2007	Transformeri
The Bourne Ultimatum	2007	Bourneov ultimatum
Pirates of the Caribbean: At World's End	2007	Pirati s Kariba: Na kraju svijeta
No Country for Old Men	2007	Nema zemlje za starce
Twilight	2008	Sumrak
Indiana Jones and the Kingdom of the Crystall Skull	2008	Indiana Jones i Kraljevstvo kristalne lubanje
The Curious Case of Benjamin Button	2008	Neobična priča o Benjaminu Buttonu
The Hangover	2009	Mamurluk
The District 9	2009	Distrikt 9
Watchmen	2009	Čuvari
Avatar	2009	Avatar
Inception	2010	Početak
Shutter Island	2010	Otok Shutter
Black Swan	2010	Crni labud
Toy Story 3	2010	Priča o igračkama 3
The King's Speech	2010	Kraljev govor

How to Train Your Dragon	2010	Kako izdresirati zmaja
The Social Network	2010	Društvena mreža
Captain America: The First Avenger	2011	Kapetan Amerika: Prvi osvjetnik
Intouchables	2011	Nedodirljivi
Drive	2011	Vožnja
Source Code	2011	Izvorni kod
Harry Potter and the Deathly Hallows: Part 2	2011	Harry Potter i Darovi smrti 2. dio
The Avengers	2012	Osvetnici
Prometheus	2012	Prometej
The Hobbit: An Unexpected Journey	2012	Hobit: Neočekivano putovanje
The Hunger Games	2012	Igre gladi
Gravity	2013	Gravitacija
Man of Steel	2013	Čovjek od čelika
The Wolf of Wall Street	2013	Vuk s Wall Streeta
World War Z	2013	Svjetski rat Z
The Hobbit: The Desolation of Smaug	2013	Hobit: Smaugova pustoš
Guardians of the Galaxy	2014	Čuvari galaksije
Gone Girl	2014	Nestala
Captain America: The Winter Soldier	2014	Kapetan Amerika: Ratnik zime
The Grand Budapest Hotel	2014	Hotel Grand Budapest
The Imitation Game	2014	Igra oponašanja
Kingsman: The Secret Service	2014	Kingsman: Tajna služba
Mad Max: Fury Road	2015	Pobješnjeli Max: Divlja cesta
The Martian	2015	Marsovac
The Revenant	2015	Povratnik
Jurassic World	2015	Jurski svijet
The Hateful Eight	2015	Mrska osmorka
Inside Out	2015	Izvrnuto obrnuto
Captain America: Civil War	2016	Kapetan Amerika: Građanski rat
Arrival	2016	Dolazak
Doctor Strange	2016	Doktor Strange
Spider-Man: Homecoming	2017	Spider-Man: Povratak kući

Get Out	2017	Bježi!
Beauty and the Beast	2017	Ljepotica i zvijer
It	2017	Ono

1.2 Free translation

A Woman of Paris: A Drama of Fate	1923	Parižanka
Three Ages	1923	Tri povijesna doba
The Hunchback of Notre Dame	1923	Zvonar crkve Notre Dame
Die Nibelungen: Siegfried	1924	Nibelunzi: Siegfridova smrt
He Who Gets Slapped	1924	Onaj kojega su tresnuli
Seven Chances	1925	Sedam sreća
Go West	1925	Na zapad
Faust: Eine deutsche Volkssage	1926	Faust
The Unknown	1927	Nepoznati
Sunrise: A Song of Two Humans	1927	Izlazak sunca – Pjesma o dva ljudska bića
La passion de Jeanne d'Arc	1928	Stradanje Ivane Orleanske
All Quiet on the Western Front	1930	Na zapadu ništa novo
Hell's Angels	1930	Pakleni anđeli
Of Human Bondage	1934	Ljudski okovi
The Thin Man	1934	Mršavko
After the Thin Man	1936	Nakon Mršavka
Way Out West	1937	Stanlio i Olio na Divljem zapadu
Captains Courageous	1937	Kapetan Hrabrosti
You Can't Take It with You	1938	U grob ništa ne nosiš
The Lady Vanishes	1938	Dama koja nestaje
La règle du jeu	1939	Pravila igre
Gone with the Wind	1939	Zameo ih vjetar
The Wolf Man	1941	Vukodlak
Sullivan's Travels	1941	Sullivanovo putovanje

I Walked with a Zombie	1943	Šetala sam se uz zombija
Double Indemnity	1944	Dvostruka obmana
Meet Me in St. Louis	1944	Srest ćemo se u St. Louisu
Spellbound	1945	Začarana
It's a Wonderful Life	1946	Divan život
Key Largo	1948	Otok Largo
Fort Apache	1948	Na apaškoj granici
Bud Abbott and Lou Costello Meet Frankenstein	1948	Abbott i Costello susreću Frankensteina
The Red Shoes	1948	Crvene cipelice
Kind Hearts and Coronets	1949	Nježno srce
The Thing from Another World	1951	Stvar
Strangers on a Train	1951	Nepoznati iz Nord Expressa
Singin' in the Rain	1952	Pjevajmo na kiši
Roman Holiday	1953	Praznik u Rimu
The Caine Mutiny	1954	Pobuna na brodu Caine
Rear Window	1954	Prozor u dvorište
On the Waterfront	1954	Na dokovima New Yorka
Dial M for Murder	1954	Nazovi M radi ubojstva
Du rififi chez les hommes	1955	Obračun među gangsterima
The Seven Year Itch	1955	Sedma godina vjernosti
To Catch a Thief	1955	Uhvatite lopova
Around the World in Eighty Days	1956	Put oko svijeta za 80 dana
Smultronstället	1957	Divlje jagode
An Affair to Remember	1957	Nešto za sjećanje
House on Haunted Hill	1959	Kuća straha
It's a Mad Mad Mad Mad World	1963	Svijet je poludio
A Shot in the Dark	1964	Pink Panther: Pucanj u tami
Dr. Strangelove or: How I Learned to Stop Worrying and Love the Bomb	1964	Dr. Strangelove ili: Kako sam naučio ne brinuti i zavolio bombu
Thunderball	1965	Operacija Grom
The Dirty Dozen	1967	12 žigosanih
Hang 'Em High	1968	Objesite ga bez milosti

On Her Majesty's Secret Service	1969	U službi njenog veličanstva
The AristoCats	1970	Mačke iz visokog društva
A Clockwork Orange	1971	Paklena naranča
Willy Wonka & the Chocolate Factory	1971	Charlie i tvornica čokolade
Diamonds are Forever	1971	Dijamanti su vječni
Everything You Always Wanted to Know About Sex * But Were Afraid to Ask	1972	Sve što ste željeli znati o seksu
Live and Let Die	1973	James Bond: Živi i pusti umrijeti
Enter the Dragon	1973	U zmajevom gnijezdu
Mean Streets	1973	Ulice nasilja
The Godfather: Part II	1974	Kum 2
The Man with the Golden Gun	1974	James Bond 007: Čovjek sa zlatnim pištoljem
The Towering Inferno	1974	Pakleni toranj
One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest	1975	Let iznad kukavičjeg gnijezda
The Man Who Would Be King	1975	Čovjek koji je htio biti kralj
The Spy Who Loved Me	1977	James Bond 007: Špijun koji me volio
A Bridge Too Far	1977	Nedostižni most
Dawn of the Dead	1978	Zora živih mrtvaca
Days of Heaven	1978	Nebeski dani
The Warriors	1979	Ratnici podzemlja
Life of Brian	1979	Brianov život
Apocalypse Now	1979	Apokalipsa danas
Mad Max	1979	Pobješnjeli Max
Star Wars: Episode V - The Empire Strikes Back	1980	Zvezdani ratovi V: Carstvo uzvraća udarac
Airplane!	1980	Ima li pilota u avionu
For Your Eyes Only	1981	James Bond 007: Samo za tvoje oči
Raiders of the Lost Ark	1981	Indiana Jones: Otimači izgubljenog kovčega
Das Boot	1981	Podmornica
The Evil Dead	1981	Zla smrt
Mad Max 2	1981	Pobješnjeli Max 2
Star Trek: The Wrath of Khan	1982	Zvezdane staze II: Khanov bijes
Star Wars: Episode VI - Return of the Jedi	1983	Zvezdani ratovi VI: Povratak Jediija

The Meaning of Life	1983	Monty Python: Smisao života
National Lampoon's Vacation	1983	Godišnji odmor snova
Mad Max Beyond Thunderdome	1985	Pobješnjeli Max 3
The Breakfast Club	1985	Klub ranoranilaca
A View to Kill	1985	Pogled na ubojstvo
Platoon	1986	Vod smrti
Evil Dead II	1987	Zla smrt II
Coming to America	1988	Princ otkriva Ameriku
The Naked Gun: From the Files of Police Squad!	1988	Goli pištolj
Big	1988	Veliki
Back to the Future Part II	1989	Povratak u budućnost II
Back to the Future Part III	1990	Povratak u budućnost III
The Godfather: Part III	1990	Kum 3
Dances with Wolves	1990	Ples s vukovima
Edward Scissorhands	1990	Edward Škaroruki
Hook	1991	Kapetan Kuka
The Silence of the Lambs	1991	Kad jaganjci utihnu
Cape Fear	1991	Rt straha
Home Alone 2: Lost in New York	1992	Sam u kući 2
Groundhog Day	1993	Beskrajni dan
The Nightmare Before Christmas	1993	Predbožićna noćna mora
Interview with the Vampire: The Vampire Chronicles	1994	Intervju s vampirom
Léon	1994	Leon profesionalac
Pulp Fiction	1994	Pakleni šund
Ace Ventura: Pet Detective	1994	Ace Ventura: Šašavi detektiv
The Lion King	1994	Kralj lavova
The Usual Suspects	1995	Privedite osumnjičene
Die Hard with a Vengeance	1995	Umri muški 3
Mission: Impossible	1996	Nemoguća misija
Romeo + Juliet	1996	Romeo i Julija
The Lost World: Jurassic Park	1997	Jurski park 2: Izgubljeni svijet
Men in Black	1997	Ljudi u crnom

There's Something About Mary	1998	Švi su ludi za Mary
A Bug's Life	1998	Život buba
Fight Club	1999	Klub boraca
Snatch	2000	Zdrpi i briši
Requiem for a Dream	2000	Rekvijem za snove
Unbreakable	2000	Neslomljivi
Mission: Impossible II	2000	Nemoguća misija 2
A Beautiful Mind	2001	Genijalni um
Monsters, Inc.	2001	Čudovišta iz ormara
Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone	2001	Harry Potter i kamen mudraca
Minority Report	2002	Specijalni izvještaj
Star Wars: Episode II - Attack of the Clones	2002	Zvezdani ratovi Epizoda II: Klonovi napadaju
Finding Nemo	2003	Potruga za Nemom
Eternal Sunshine of the Spotless Mind	2004	Vječni sjaj nepobjedivog uma
Million Dollar Baby	2004	Djevojka od milijun dolara
Batman Begins	2005	Batman: Početak
The 40 Year Old Virgin	2005	Junfer u četrdesetoj
Little Miss Sunshine	2006	Mala miss Amerike
Children of Men	2006	Djeca čovječanstva
Into the Wild	2007	U divljini
Slumdog Millionaire	2008	Milijunaš s ulice
The Dark Knight	2008	Vitez tame
Zombieland	2009	Dobrodošli u zemlju zombija
Inglourious Basterds	2009	Nemilosrdni gadovi
(500) Days of Summer	2009	(500) dana ljubavi
Star Trek	2009	Zvezdane staze
Rise of the Planet of the Apes	2011	Planet majmuna: Postanak
The Hangover Part II	2011	Mamurluk 2
X: First Class	2011	X-Men: Prva generacija
The Dark Knight Rises	2012	Vitez tame: Povratak
Django Unchained	2012	Odbjegli Django
The Hunger Games: Catching Fire	2013	Igre gladi: Plamen

12 Years a Slave	2013	12 godina ropstva
Edge of Tomorrow	2014	Na rubu budućnosti
Gone Girl	2014	Nestala
Star Wars: Episode VII – The Force Awakens	2015	Ratovi zvijezda: Sila se budi
Avengers: Age of Ultron	2015	Osvetnici 2: Vladavina Ultrona
Zootopia	2016	Zootropola
Baby Driver	2017	Vozač

1.3 Transcreation

Safety Last!	1923	Napokon spas!
Battling Butler	1926	Buster, boksački šampion
The Cocoanuts	1929	Braća Marx: Tvrde glave
Animal Crackers	1930	Krotitelji
Gold Diggers of 1933	1933	Lov na sreću
Bringing Up Baby	1938	Silom dadilja
Now, Voyager	1942	Na raskršću
The Ox-Bow Incident	1943	Omča za vješanje
Murder, My Sweet	1944	Zbogom ljepotice
White Heat	1949	Usijanje
Twelve O'Clock High	1949	Polijetanje usred dana
Scrooge	1951	Božićna priča
The Bad and the Beautiful	1952	Grad iluzija
The Ladykillers	1955	Gangsterska petorka
The Killing	1956	Uzaludna pljačka
The Wrong Man	1956	Krivo optužen
Kumonosu-jô	1957	Krvavo prijestolje
Såsom i en spegel	1961	Kroz tamno ogledalo
The Haunting	1963	Kuća duhova
The Sound of Music	1965	Moje pjesme, moji snovi

Cool Hand Luke	1967	Hladnokrvni kažnjenik
Where Eagle Dares	1968	Orlovo gnijezdo
Easy Rider	1969	Goli u sedlu
True Gift	1969	Čovjek zvan Hrabrost
Kelly's Heroes	1970	Zlato za odvažne
The Conversation	1974	Prisluškivanje
Moonraker	1979	James Bond 007: Operacija Svemir
Caddyshack	1980	Golf klub
Stripes	1981	Vojničine
Blade Runner	1982	Istrebljivač
First Blood	1982	Rambo
Trading Places	1983	Kolo sreće
Aliens	1986	Alien 2
Die Hard	1988	Umri muški
Beetlejuice	1988	Bubimir
Die Hard 2	1990	Umri muški 2
Point Break	1991	Pakleni val
Unforgiven	1992	Nepomirljivi
Basic Instinct	1992	Sirove strasti
Mrs. Doubtfire	1993	Tatica u suknji
Clerks	1993	Trgovci
Face/Off	1997	Čovjek bez lica
American History X	1998	Generacija X
Lock, Stock and the Two Smoking Barrels	1998	Lopovi, ubojice i dvije nabijene puške
American Beauty	1999	Vrtlog života
Cast Away	2000	Brodolom života
Meet the Parents	2000	Dozvola za brak
Sen to Chihiro no kamikakushi	2001	Avanture male Chihiro
Oldeuboi	2003	Oldboy
The Incredibles	2004	Izbavitelji
The Notebook	2004	Zima za dvoje
Shaun of the Dead	2004	Noć glupih mrtvaca

Ratatouille	2007	Juhu-hu
Taken	2008	96 sati
Up	2009	Nebesa
Despicable Me	2010	Kako je Gru ukrao mjesec
Limitless	2011	Savršena formula
Silver Linings Playbook	2012	U dobru i u zlu
Now You See Me	2013	Majstori iluzije
Frozen	2013	Snježno kraljevstvo
Whiplash	2014	Ritam ludila
Suicide Squad	2016	Odred otpisanih

1.4 Transcription

Sherlock Jr.	1924	Sherlock Jr.
Metropolis	1927	Metropolis
Cimarron	1931	Cimarron
Frankenstein	1931	Frankenstein
M	1931	M
Tabu: A Story of the South Seas	1931	Tabu
Grand Hotel	1932	Grand Hotel
King Kong	1933	King Kong
Dodsworth	1936	Dodsworth
Jezebel	1938	Jezebel
Aleksandr Nevskiy	1938	Alexander Nevsky
Pygmalion	1938	Pygmalion
Ninotchka	1939	Ninočka
Pinocchio	1940	Pinocchio
Rebecca	1940	Rebecca
Dumbo	1941	Dumbo
The Lady Eve	1941	Lady Eve

Yankee Doodle Dandy	1942	Yankee Doodle Dandy
Casablanca	1942	Casablanca
Bambi	1942	Bambi
Holiday Inn	1942	Holiday Inn
Jane Eyre	1943	Jane Eyre
Laura	1944	Laura
Mildred Pierce	1945	Mildred Pierce
Gilda	1947	Gilda
Hamlet	1948	Hamlet
Winchester '73	1950	Winchester '73
Rio Grande	1950	Rio Grande
Rashômon	1950	Rašomon
Umberto D.	1952	Umberto D
Stalag 17	1953	Stalag 17
Shane	1953	Shane
Sabrina	1954	Sabrina
Gojira	1954	Godzilla
Gigi	1958	Gigi
Ben-Hur	1959	Ben-Hur
Rio Bravo	1959	Rio Bravo
Spartacus	1960	Spartak
Viridiana	1961	Viridiana
Dr. No	1962	Dr. No
Lolita	1962	Lolita
The Pink Panther	1963	Pink Panther
Goldfinger	1964	Goldfinger
Mary Poppins	1964	Mary Poppins
Marnie	1964	Marnie
Zulu	1964	Zulu
Persona	1966	Persona
Fahrenheit 451	1966	Fahrenheit 451
Andrey Rublev	1966	Andrej Rubljov

Chitty Chitty Bang Bang	1968	Chitty Chitty Bang Bang
Bullitt	1968	Bullitt
Z	1969	Z
MASH	1970	M.A.S.H.
Patton	1970	Patton
Tora! Tora! Tora!	1970	Tora! Tora! Tora!
THX 1138	1971	THX 1138
Cabaret	1972	Cabaret
Solyaris	1972	Solaris
Robin Hood	1973	Robin Hood
Serpico	1973	Serpico
Barry Lyndon	1975	Barry Lyndon
The Rocky Horror Picture Show	1975	Rocky Horror Picture Show
Rocky	1976	Rocky
Carrie	1976	Carrie
Annie Hall	1977	Annie Hall
Eraserhead	1977	Eraserhead
Suspiria	1977	Suspiria
Superman	1978	Superman
Rocky II	1979	Rocky 2
Manhattan	1979	Manhattan
Alien	1979	Alien: Osmi putnik
Superman II	1980	Superman 2
Poltergeist	1982	Poltergeist
TRON	1982	Tron
Gandhi	1982	Gandhi
Rocky III	1982	Rocky 3
E.T. the Extra-Terrestrial	1982	E.T.
Octopussy	1983	James Bond: Octopussy
Amadeus	1984	Amadeus
The Karate Kid	1984	Karate Kid
Ran	1985	Ran

Rocky IV	1985	Rocky 4
Rambo: First Blood Part II	1985	Rambo 2
The Goonies	1985	Goonies
Top Gun	1986	Top Gun
RoboCop	1987	Robocop
Full Metal Jacket	1987	Full Metal Jacket
Wall Street	1987	Wall Street
Batman	1989	Batman
JFK	1991	JFK
Aladdin	1992	Aladdin
Alien ³	1992	Alien 3
Philadelphia	1993	Philadelphia
Forrest Gump	1994	Forrest Gump
Apollo 13	1995	Apollo 13
Jumanji	1995	Jumanji
Trainspotting	1996	Trainspotting
Fargo	1996	Fargo
Jerry Maguire	1996	Jerry Maguire
Titanic	1997	Titanic
Armageddon	1998	Armageddon
Blade	1998	Blade
The Matrix	1999	Matrix
Memento	2000	Memento
X-Men	2000	X-Men
Donnie Darko	2001	Donnie Darko
Shrek	2001	Shrek
Spider-Man	2002	Spider-Man
X-Men 2	2003	X-Men 2
Kill Bill: Vol. 1	2003	Kill Bill
The Matrix Reloaded	2003	Matrix Reloaded
The Matrix Revolutions	2003	Matrix: Revolutions
Spider-Man 2	2004	Spider-Man 2

Kill Bill: Vol. 2	2004	Kill Bill 2
Sin City	2005	Sin City
King Kong	2005	King Kong
300	2006	300
Casino Royale	2006	Casino Royale
Superbad	2007	Superbad
Juno	2007	Juno
Spider-Man 3	2007	Spider-Man 3
WALL·E	2008	WALL·E
Iron Man	2008	Iron Man
Gran Torino	2008	Gran Torino
Hancock	2008	Hancock
Sherlock Holmes	2009	Sherlock Holmes
Iron Man 2	2010	Iron Man 2
Kick-Ass	2010	Kick Ass
Thor	2011	Thor
Skyfall	2012	Skyfall
Ted	2012	Ted
Argo	2012	Argo
Iron Man Three	2013	Iron Man 3
Interstellar	2014	Interstellar
Ant-Man	2015	Ant-Man
Ex Machina	2015	Ex Machina
Deadpool	2016	Deadpool
X-Men: Apocalypse	2016	X-Men: Apocalypse
La La Land	2016	La La Land
Wonder Woman	2017	Wonder Woman
Dunkirk	2017	Dunkirk
Logan	2017	Logan: Wolverine
John Wick: Chapter 2	2017	John Wick 2

1.5 Combinations of translation and transcription (CTTs)

Steamboat Bill, Jr.	1928	Steamboat Bill ml.
Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde	1931	Dr. Jekyll i Mr. Hyde
X-Men: The Last Stand	2006	X-Men: Posljednja fronta
X-Men: Days of Future Past	2014	X-Men: Dani buduće prošlosti
Batman v Superman: Dawn of Justice	2016	Batman v Superman: Zora pravednika
Rogue One: A Star Wars Story	2016	Rogue One: Priča iz Ratova zvijezda
Guardians of the Galaxy Vol. 2	2017	Čuvari galaksije Vol. 2

2. German subcorpus

2.1 Direct translation

La souriante Madame Beudet	1923	Das Lächeln der Madame Beudet
The Pilgrim	1923	Der Pilger
Three Ages	1923	Drei Zeitalter
The Love Nest	1923	Das Liebesnest
The Ten Commandments	1923	Die zehn Gebote
Greed	1924	Gier
The Navigator	1924	Der Navigator
The Thief of Bagdad	1924	Der Dieb von Bagdad
Girl Shy	1924	Mädchenscheu
The Gold Rush	1925	Der Goldrausch
The Big Parade	1925	Die große Parade
The Lost World	1925	Die verlorene Welt
Bronenosets Potyomkin	1925	Panzerkreuzer Potemkin
Stachka	1925	Streik
The Phantom of the Opera	1925	Das Phantom der Oper

Seven Chances	1925	Sieben Chancen
The Lost World	1925	Die verlorene Welt
The General	1926	Der General
Mat	1926	Die Mutter
Kurutta ippêji	1926	Eine Seite des Wahnsinns
The Son of the Sheik	1926	Der Sohn des Scheichs
Sunrise: A Song of Two Humans	1927	Sonnenaufgang – Lied von zwei Menschen
The Kid Brother	1927	Der kleine Bruder
The Jazz Singer	1927	Der Jazzsänger
La passion de Jeanne d'Arc	1928	Die Passion der Jungfrau von Orléans
The Circus	1928	Der Zirkus
The Cameraman	1928	Der Kameramann
Oktyabr	1928	Oktober
The Wind	1928	Der Wind
The Man Who Laughs	1928	Der Mann, der lacht
Un chien andalou	1929	Ein andalusischer Hund
Blackmail	1929	Erpressung
The Skeleton Dance	1929	Tanz der Skelette
Chelovek s kino-apparatom	1929	Der Mann mit der Kamera
L'âge d'or	1930	Das goldene Zeitalter
Zemlya	1930	Erde
The Public Enemy	1931	Der öffentliche Feind
City Lights	1931	Lichter der Großstadt
Little Caesar	1931	Der kleine Cäsar
The Mummy	1932	Die Mumie
Scarface	1932	Narbengesicht
Queen Christina	1933	Königin Christine
Gold Diggers of 1933	1933	Goldgräber von 1933
42nd Street	1933	Die 42. Straße
Dinner at Eight	1933	Dinner um acht
It Happened One Night	1934	Es geschah in einer Nacht
The Thin Man	1934	Der dünne Mann

The Man Who Knew Too Much	1934	Der Mann, der zuviel wusste
The Black Cat	1934	Die schwarze Katze
The Scarlet Empress	1934	Die scharlachrote Kaiserin
Bride of Frankenstein	1935	Frankensteins Braut
The 39 Steps	1935	Die 39 Stufen
Mutiny on the Bounty	1935	Meuterei auf der Bounty
Modern Times	1936	Moderne Zeiten
My Man Godfrey	1936	Mein Mann Godfrey
Mr. Deeds Goes to Town	1936	Mr. Deeds geht in die Stadt
Sabotage	1936	Sabotage
The Petrified Forest	1936	Der versteinerte Wald
Otto e mezzo	1936	Achteinhalb
La grande illusion	1937	Die große Illusion
The Awful Truth	1937	Die schreckliche Wahrheit
Young and Innocent	1937	Jung und unschuldig
Stage Door	1937	Bühneneingang
Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs	1937	Schneewittchen und die sieben Zwerge
Le quai des brumes	1938	Hafen im Nebel
La règle du jeu	1939	Die Spielregel
The Women	1939	Die Frauen
The Roaring Twenties	1939	Die wilden Zwanziger
The Wizard of Oz	1939	Der Zauberer von Oz
Wuthering Heights	1939	Sturmhöhe
The Great Dictator	1940	Der große Diktator
Foreign Correspondent	1940	Der Auslandskorrespondent
The Thief of Bagdad	1940	Der Dieb von Bagdad
The Grapes of Wrath	1940	Früchte des Zorns
Citizen Kane	1941	Bürger Kane
Suspicion	1941	Verdacht
Sullivan's Travels	1941	Sullivans Reisen
The Wolf Man	1941	Der Wolfmensch
To Be or Not to Be	1942	Sein oder Nichtsein

Cat People	1942	Katzenmenschen
Le corbeau	1943	Der Rabe
For Whom the Bell Tolls	1943	Wem die Stunde schlägt
Lifeboat	1944	Das Rettungsboot
The Three Caballeros	1944	Drei Caballeros
Murder, My Sweet	1944	Mord, meine Lieblich
Roma città aperta	1945	Rom, offene Stadt
The Lost Weekend	1945	Das verlorene Wochenende
Detour	1945	Umleitung
The Picture of Dorian Gray	1945	Das Bildnis des Dorian Gray
Notorious	1946	Berüchtigt
The Best Years of Our Lives	1946	Die besten Jahre unseres Lebens
The Lady from Shanghai	1947	Die Lady von Schanghai
The Paradine Case	1947	Der Fall Paradin
Black Narcissus	1947	Die schwarze Narzisse
Ladri di biciclette	1948	Fahrraddiebe
The Treasure of the Sierra Madre	1948	Der Schatz der Sierra Madre
The Red Shoes	1948	Die roten Schuhe
The Heiress	1949	Die Erbin
The Third Man	1949	Der dritte Mann
Nora inu	1949	Ein streunender Hund
All About Eve	1950	Alles über Eva
The Asphalt Jungle	1950	Asphalt-Dschungel
Los ovidados	1950	Die Vergessenen
The Day the Earth Stood Still	1951	Der Tag, an dem die Erde stillstand
The Thing from Another World	1951	Das Ding aus einer anderen Welt
A Place in the Sun	1951	Ein Platz an der Sonne
Alice in Wonderland	1951	Alice im Wunderland
High Noon	1952	Zwölf Uhr Mittags
Limelight	1952	Rampenlicht
The Greatest Show on Earth	1952	Die größte Schau der Welt
Jeux interdits	1952	Verbotene Spiele

Le salaire de la peur	1953	Lohn der Angst
The War of the Worlds	1953	Kampf der Welten
White Christmas	1954	Weiße Weihnachten
Shichinin no samurai	1954	Die sieben Samurai
20,000 Leagues Under the Sea	1954	20 000 Meilen unter dem Meer
Les diaboliques	1955	Die Teuflischen
The Night of the Hunter	1955	Die Nacht des Jägers
The Ten Commandments	1956	Die zehn Gebote
The Man Who Knew Too Much	1956	Der Mann, der zuviel wusste
The King and I	1956	Der König und ich
The Wrong Man	1956	Der falsche Mann
Around the World in Eighty Days	1956	In 80 Tagen um die Welt
Le notti di Cabiria	1957	Die Nächte der Cabiria
Witness for the Prosecution	1957	Zeugin der Klage
Det sjunde inseglet	1957	Das siebente Siegel
Mon oncle	1958	Mein Onkel
Cat on a Hot Tin Roof	1958	Die Katze auf dem heißen Blechdach
Ascenseur pour l'échafaud	1958	Fahrstuhl zum Schafott
The Fly	1958	Die Fliege
Some Like It Hot	1959	Manche mögen's heiß
Plan 9 from Outer Space	1959	Plan 9 aus dem Weltall
House on Haunted Hill	1959	Das Haus auf dem Geisterhügel
Sleeping Beauty	1959	Dornröschen
Anatomy of a Murder	1959	Anatomie eines Mordes
The Apartment	1960	Das Appartement
The Magnificent Seven	1960	Die glorreichen Sieben
À bout de souffle	1960	Außer Atem
La dolce vita	1960	Das süße Leben
The Time Machine	1960	Die Zeitmaschine
Jungfrukällan	1960	Die Jungfrauenquelle
Breakfast at Tiffany's	1961	Frühstück bei Tiffany
One Hundred and One Dalmatians	1961	101 Dalmatiner

The Guns of Navarone	1961	Die Kanonen von Navarone
Såsom i en spegel	1961	Wie in einem Spiegel
Lawrence of Arabia	1962	Lawrence von Arabien
The Man Who Shot Liberty Valance	1962	Der Mann, der Liberty Valance erschöß
The Longest Day	1962	Der längste Tag
What Ever Happened to Baby Jane?	1962	Was geschah wirklich mit Baby Jane?
Jules et Jim	1962	Jules und Jim
The Pink Panther	1963	Der rosarote Panther
The Birds	1963	Die Vögel
A Shot in the Dark	1964	Ein Schuß im Dunkeln
Per un pugno di dollari	1964	Für eine Handvoll Dollar
Repulsion	1965	Ekel
The Flight of the Phoenix	1965	Der Flug des Phönix
Per qualche dollaro in più	1965	Für ein paar Dollar mehr
Doctor Zhivago	1965	Doktor Schiwago
A Man for All Seasons	1966	Ein Mann zu jeder Jahreszeit
La battaglia di Algeri	1966	Schlacht um Algier
Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?	1966	Wer hat Angst vor Virginia Woolf?
The Dirty Dozen	1967	Das dreckige Dutzend
In the Heat of the Night	1967	In der Hitze der Nacht
Bonnie and Clyde	1967	Bonnie und Clyde
The Jungle Book	1967	Das Dschungelbuch
2001: A Space Odyssey	1968	2001: Odyssee im Weltraum
Rosemary's Baby	1968	Rosemaries Baby
Night of the Living Dead	1968	Die Nacht der lebenden Toten
Planet of the Apes	1968	Planet der Affen
L'armée des ombres	1969	Armee im Schatten
A Clockwork Orange	1971	Uhrwerk Orange
Duel	1971	Duell
The Godfather	1972	Der Pate
Ultimo tango a Parigi	1972	Der letzte Tango in Paris
The Exorcist	1973	Der Exorzist

Young Frankenstein	1974	Frankenstein Junior
Murder on the Orient Express	1974	Mord im Orient Express
One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest	1975	Einer flog über das Kuckucksnest
Three Days of the Condor	1975	Die drei Tage des Condor
The Omen	1976	Das Omen
Marathon Man	1976	Der Marathon-Mann
Life of Brian	1979	Das Leben des Brian
Kramer vs. Kramer	1979	Kramer gegen Kramer
Escape from Alcatraz	1979	Flucht von Alcatraz
The Elephant Man	1980	Der Elefantenmensch
Friday the 13th	1980	Freitag der 13.
The Blue Lagoon	1980	Die blaue Lagune
E.T. the Extra-Terrestrial	1982	E.T. – Der Außerirdische
Conan the Barbarian	1982	Conan der Barbar
The Meaning of Life	1983	Der Sinn des Lebens
Back to the Future	1985	Zurück in die Zukunft
The Goonies	1985	Die Goonies
Tenkû no shiro Rapyuta	1986	Das Schloss im Himmel
The Princess Bride	1987	Die Braut des Prinzen
Tonari no Totoro	1988	Mein Nachbar Totoro
Indiana Jones and the Last Crusade	1989	Indiana Jones und der letzte Kreuzzug
Dead Poets Society	1989	Der Club der toten Dichter
Honey, I Shrunk the Kids	1989	Liebling, ich habe die Kinder geschrumpft
Back to the Future Part II	1989	Zurück in die Zukunft II
Back to the Future Part III	1990	Zurück in die Zukunft III
The Silence of the Lambs	1991	Das Schweigen der Lämmer
Beauty and the Beast	1991	Die Schöne und das Biest
Cape Fear	1991	Kap der Angst
Terminator 2: Judgment Day	1991	Terminator 2 – Tag der Abrechnung
Terminator 2: Judgment Day	1991	Terminator 2 – Tag der Abrechnung
Schindler's List	1993	Schindlers Liste
Dumb & Dumber	1994	Dumm und Dümmer

The Mask	1994	Die Maske
The Usual Suspects	1995	Die üblichen Verdächtigen
Se7en	1995	Sieben
Le cinquième élément	1997	Das fünfte Element
La vita è bella	1997	Das Leben ist schön
The Truman Show	1998	Die Truman Show
The Mummy	1999	Die Mumie
The Pianist	2002	Der Pianist
The Bourne Identity	2002	Die Bourne Identität
The Lord of the Rings: The Two Towers	2002	Der Herr der Ringe: Die zwei Türme
The Lord of the Rings: The Return of the King	2003	Der Herr der Ringe: Die Rückkehr des Königs
Troy	2004	Troja
Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban	2004	Harry Potter und der Gefangene von Askaban
V for Vendetta	2005	V wie Vendetta
Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire	2005	Harry Potter und der Feuerkelch
War of the Worlds	2005	Krieg der Welten
Charlie and the Chocolate Factory	2005	Charlie und die Schokoladenfabrik
The Bourne Ultimatum	2007	Das Bourne Ultimatum
Indiana Jones and the Kingdom of the Crystall Skull	2008	Indiana Jones und das Königreich des Kristallschädels
The Curious Case of Benjamin Button	2008	Der seltsame Fall des Benjamin Button
Up	2009	Oben
Harry Potter and the Deathly Hollows: Part 2	2011	Harry Potter und die Heiligtümer des Todes – Teil 2
The Hobbit: An Unexpected Journey	2012	Der Hobbit: Eine unerwartete Reise
The Hobbit: The Desolation of Smaug	2013	Der Hobbit: Smaugs Einöde
John Wick: Chapter 2	2017	John Wick: Kapitel 2
The Beauty and the Beast	2017	Die Schöne und das Biest
It	2017	Es

2.2 Free translation

Our Hospitality	1923	Verflixte Gastfreundschaft
The Hunchback of Notre Dame	1923	Der Glöckner von Notre Dame
He Who Gets Slapped	1924	Der Mann, der die Ohrfeigen bekam
Ben-Hur: A Tale of the Christ	1925	Ben Hur
The Black Pirate	1926	Der Seeräuber
Napoléon vu par Abel Gance	1927	Napoleon
The Lodger: A Story of the London Fog	1927	Der Mieter
Big Business	1929	Laurel und Hardy: Das große Geschäft
Murder!	1930	Mord – Sir John greift ein!
Morocco	1930	Marokko – Herzen in Flammen
Hell's Angels	1930	Höllenflieger
The Big Trail	1930	Der große Treck
All Quiet on the Western Front	1930	Im Westen nichts Neues
Trouble in Paradise	1932	Ärger im Paradies
Grand Hotel	1932	Menschen im Hotel
The Invisible Man	1933	Der Unsichtbare
Sons of the Desert	1933	Laurel und Hardy: Die Wüstensöhne
A Night at the Opera	1935	Skandal in der Oper
Fury	1936	Blinde Wut
After the Thin Man	1936	Dünner Mann, 2. Fall
A Day at the Races	1937	Die Marx Brothers: Ein Tag beim Rennen
A Star Is Born	1937	Ein Stern geht auf
The Lady Vanishes	1938	Eine Dame verschwindet
The Lady Vanishes	1938	Eine Dame verschwindet
Angels with Dirty Faces	1938	Chicago – Engel mit schmutzigen Gesichtern
The Adventures of Robin Hood	1938	Robin Hood, König der Vagabunden
Gone with the Wind	1939	Vom Winde verweht
The Maltese Falcon	1941	Die Spur des Falken
High Sierra	1941	Entscheidung in der Sierra

Saboteur	1942	Saboteure
The Magnificent Ambersons	1942	Der Glanz des Hauses Amberson
Shadow of a Doubt	1943	Im Schatten des Zweifels
Vredens dag	1943	Tag der Rache
The Ox-Bow Incident	1943	Ritt zum Ox-Bow
The Life and Death of Colonel Blimp	1943	Leben und Sterben des Colonel Blimp
To Have and Have Not	1944	Haben und Nichthaben
Arsenic and Old Lace	1944	Arsen und Spitzenhäubchen
Brief Encounter	1945	Begegnung
Scarlet Street	1945	Straße der Versuchung
Les enfants du paradis	1945	Kinder des Olymp
Miracle on 34th Street	1947	Das Wunder von Manhattan
Dark Passage	1947	Die schwarze Natter
The Ghost and Mrs. Muir	1947	Ein Gespenst auf Freiersfüßen
Bud Abbott and Lou Costello Meet Frankenstein	1948	Abbott und Costello treffen Frankenstein
The Naked City	1948	Stadt ohne Maske
In a Lonely Place	1950	Ein einsamer Ort
Strangers on a Train	1951	Der Fremde im Zug
A Streetcar Named Desire	1951	Endstation Sehnsucht
Gentlemen Prefer Blondes	1953	Blondinen bevorzugt
Tôkyô monogatari	1953	Die Reise nach Tokio
From Here to Eternity	1953	Verdammt in alle Ewigkeit
Dial M for Murder	1954	Bei Anruf Mord
Rear Window	1954	Das Fenster zum Hof
The Caine Mutiny	1954	Die Caine war ihr Schicksal
Du rififi chez les hommes	1955	Rififi
East of Eden	1955	Jenseits von Eden
The Trouble with Harry	1955	Immer Ärger mit Harry
The Seven Year Itch	1955	Das verflixte 7. Jahr
Giant	1956	Giganten
The Bridge on the River Kwai	1957	Die Brücke am Kwei
Smultronstället	1957	Wilde Erdbeeren

Paths of Glory	1957	Wege zum Ruhm
12 Angry Men	1957	Die zwölf Geschworenen
Kakushi-toride no san-akunin	1958	Die verborgene Festung
Touch of Evil	1958	Im Zeichen des Bösen
Judgment at Nuremberg	1961	Das Urteil von Nürnberg
It's a Mad Mad Mad Mad World	1963	Eine total, total verrückte Welt
From Russia with Love	1963	James Bond 007 – Liebesgrüße aus Moskau
Rudolph, the Red-Nosed Reindeer	1964	Rudolph mit der roten Nase
Dr. Strangelove or: How I Learned to Stop Worrying and Love the Bomb	1964	Dr. Seltsam, oder wie ich lernte, die Bombe zu lieben
Help!	1965	Hi-Hi-Hilfe!
Thunderball	1965	James Bond 007 – Feuerball
You Only Live Twice	1967	James Bond 007 – Man lebt nur zweimal
Hang 'Em High	1968	Hängt ihn höher
The Party	1968	Der Partyschreck
On Her Majesty's Secret Service	1969	James Bond 007 – Im Geheimdienst Ihrer Majestät
Midnight Cowboy	1969	Asphalt-Cowboy
Battle of Britain	1969	Luftschlacht um England
Beneath the Planet of the Apes	1970	Rückkehr zum Planet der Affen
Willy Wonka & the Chocolate Factory	1971	Charlie und die Schokoladenfabrik
The Last Picture Show	1971	Die letzte Vorstellung
Diamonds are Forever	1971	James Bond 007 – Diamantenfieber
Everything You Always Wanted to Know About Sex * But Were Afraid to Ask	1972	Was Sie schon immer über Sex wissen wollten
The Poseidon Adventure	1972	Die Höllenfahrt der Poseidon
Live and Let Die	1973	James Bond 007 – Leben und sterben lassen
The Godfather: Part II	1974	Der Pate 2
The Conversation	1974	Der Dialog
The Towering Inferno	1974	Flammendes Inferno
The Man with the Golden Gun	1974	James Bond 007 – Der Mann mit dem goldenen Colt
Dog Day Afternoon	1975	Hundstage
Salò o le 120 giornate di Sodoma	1975	Die 120 Tage von Sodom

The Man Who Would Be King	1975	Der Mann, der König sein wollte
The Enforcer	1976	Dirty Harry III – Der Unerbittliche
Logan's Run	1976	Flucht ins 23. Jahrhundert
Star Wars	1977	Krieg der Sterne
The Spy Who Loved Me	1977	James Bond 007 – Der Spion, der mich liebte
A Bridge Too Far	1977	Die Brücke von Arnheim
Close Encounters of the Third Kind	1977	Unheimliche Begegnung der dritten Art
Invasion of the Body Snatchers	1978	Die Körperfresser kommen
Star Wars: Episode V – The Empire Strikes Back	1980	Das Imperium schlägt zurück
Airplane!	1980	Die unglaubliche Reise in einem verrückten Flugzeug
Raging Bull	1980	Wie ein wilder Stier
Raiders of the Lost Ark	1981	Jäger des verlorenen Schatzes
The Thing	1982	Das Ding aus einer anderen Welt
Star Trek: The Wrath of Khan	1982	Star Trek II: Der Zorn des Khan
Star Wars: Episode VI – Return of the Jedi	1983	Die Rückkehr der Jedi-Ritter
A Christmas Story	1983	Fröhliche Weihnachten
Risky Business	1983	Lockere Geschäfte
Star Wars: Episode VI – Return of the Jedi	1983	Die Rückkehr der Jedi-Ritter
Indiana Jones and the Temple of Doom	1984	Indiana Jones und der Tempel des Todes
Commando	1985	Das Phantom Kommando
Mad Max Beyond Thunderdome	1985	Mad Max III – Jenseits der Donnerkuppel
Labyrinth	1986	Die Reise ins Labyrinth
Ferris Bueller's Day Off	1986	Ferris macht blau
The Naked Gun: From the Files of Police Squad!	1988	Die nackte Kanone
Die Hard	1988	Stirb langsam
Who Framed Roger Rabbit	1988	Falsches Spiel mit Roger Rabbit
Hotaru no haka	1988	Die letzten Glühwürmchen
Back to the Future Part II	1989	Zurück in die Zukunft II
When Harry Met Sally...	1989	Harry und Sally
The Little Mermaid	1989	Arielle, die Meerjungfrau
The Godfather: Part III	1990	Der Pate 3
Back to the Future Part III	1990	Zurück in die Zukunft III

Edward Scissorhands	1990	Edward mit den Scherenhänden
Dances with Wolves	1990	Der mit dem Wolf tanzt
Home Alone	1990	Kevin – Allein zu Haus
Die Hard 2	1990	Stirb langsam 2
Robin Hood: Prince of Thieves	1991	Robin Hood – König der Diebe
Batman Returns	1992	Batmans Rückkehr
Scent of a Woman	1992	Der Duft der Frauen
Groundhog Day	1993	Und täglich grüßt das Murmeltier
What's Eating Gilbert Grape	1993	Gilbert Grape – Irgendwo in Iowa
The Lion King	1994	Der König der Löwen
Ace Ventura: Pet Detective	1994	Ace Ventura – Ein tierischer Detektiv
Interview with the Vampire: The Vampire Chronicles	1994	Interview mit einem Vampir
The Devil's Advocate	1997	Im Auftrag des Teufels
There's Something About Mary	1998	Verrückt nach Mary
Saving Private Ryan	1998	Der Soldat James Ryan
Monsters, Inc.	2001	Die Monster AG
The Lord of the Rings: The Fellowship of the Ring	2001	Der Herr der Ringe: Die Gefährten
Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone	2001	Harry Potter und der Stein der Weisen
Le fabuleux destin d'Amélie Poulain	2001	Die fabelhafte Welt der Amélie
Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets	2002	Harry Potter und die Kammer des Schreckens
Finding Nemo	2003	Findet Nemo
The 40 Year Old Virgin	2005	Jungfrau (40), männlich, sucht ...
El laberinto del fauno	2006	Pans Labyrinth
How to Train Your Dragon	2010	Drachenzähmen leicht gemacht
Limitless	2011	Ohne Limit
Rise of the Planet of the Apes	2011	Planet der Affen: Prevolution
Frozen	2013	Die Eiskönigin – Völlig unverfroren
Star Wars: Episode VII – The Force Awakens	2015	Star Wars: Episode VII – Das Erwachen der Macht
Inside Out	2015	Alles steht Kopf
The Martian	2015	Der Marsianer – Rettet Mark Watney
Zootopia	2016	Zoomania

2.3 Transcreation

Safety Last!	1923	Ausgerechnet Wolkenkratzer!
A Woman of Paris: A Drama of Fate	1923	Die Nächte einer schönen Frau
The Freshman	1925	Der Sportstudent
Go West	1925	Der Cowboy
Flesh and the Devil	1926	Es war
Battling Butler	1926	Der Killer von Alabama
College	1927	Der Musterschüler
The Crowd	1928	Ein Mensch der Masse
Show People	1928	Es tut sich was in Hollywood
Monkey Business	1931	Die Marx Brothers auf See
Cimarron	1931	Pioniere des Wilden Westens
Horse Feathers	1932	Blühender Blödsinn
I Am a Fugitive from a Chain Gang	1932	Jagd auf James A.
The Most Dangerous Game	1932	Graf Zaroff – Genie des Bösen
Duck Soup	1933	Die Marx Brothers im Krieg
The Gay Divorcee	1934	Tanz mit mir!
Twentieth Century	1934	Napoleon vom Broadway
Babes in Toyland	1934	Laurel und Hardy: Rache ist süß
Top Hat	1935	Ich tanz' mich in dein Herz hinein
Captain Blood	1935	Unter Piratenflagge
The Informer	1935	Der Verräter
A Tale of Two Cities	1935	Flucht aus Paris
Dodsworth	1936	Zeit der Liebe, Zeit des Abschieds
Way Out West	1937	Laurel und Hardy: Zwei ritten nach Texas
Lost Horizon	1937	In den Fesseln von Shangri-La
Captains Courageous	1937	Manuel
Holiday	1938	Die Schwester der Braut
Pygmalion	1938	Der Roman eines Blumenmädchens
Bringing Up Baby	1938	Leoparden küsst man nicht

You Can't Take It with You	1938	Lebenskünstler
Stagecoach	1939	Ringo
Only Angles Have Wings	1939	S.O.S. Feuer an Bord
The Philadelphia Story	1940	Die Nacht vor der Hochzeit
His Girl Friday	1940	Sein Mädchen für besondere Fälle
The Shop Around the Corner	1940	Rendezvous nach Ladenschluss
The Lady Eve	1941	Die Falschspielerin
How Green Was My Valley	1941	Schlagende Wetter
Holiday Inn	1942	Musik, Musik
Now, Voyager	1942	Reise aus der Vergangenheit
Heaven Can Wait	1943	Ein himmlischer Sünder
Gaslight	1944	Das Haus der Lady Alquist
The Woman in the Window	1944	Gefährliche Begegnungen
Double Indemnity	1944	Frau ohne Gewissen
Spellbound	1945	Ich kämpfe um dich
Mildred Pierce	1945	Solange ein Herz schlägt
And Then There Were None	1945	Das letzte Wochenende
La belle et la bête	1946	Es war einmal
My Darling Clementine	1946	Faustrecht der Prärie
It's a Wonderful Life	1946	Ist das Leben nicht schön
The Big Sleep	1946	Tote schlafen fest
Great Expectations	1946	Geheimnisvolle Erbschaft
The Postman Always Rings Twice	1946	Im Netz der Leidenschaft
The Killers	1946	Rache der Unterwelt
Out of the Past	1947	Goldenes Gift
Gentlemen's Agreement	1947	Tabu der Gerechten
The Bishop's Wife	1947	Jede Frau braucht einen Engel
Rope	1948	Cocktail für eine Leiche
Key Largo	1948	Hafen des Lasters
Fort Apache	1948	Bis zum letzten Mann
Kind Hearts and Coronets	1949	Adel verpflichtet
White Heat	1949	Sprung in den Tod

Adam's Rib	1949	Ehekrieg
She Wore a Yellow Ribbon	1949	Der Teufelshauptmann
Twelve O'Clock High	1949	Der Kommandeur
All the King's Men	1949	Der Mann, der herrschen wollte
Ace in the Hole	1951	Reporter des Satans
Scrooge	1951	Charles Dickens - Eine Weihnachtsgeschichte
Singin' in the Rain	1952	Du sollst mein Glücksstern sein
Monkey Business	1952	Liebling, ich werde jünger
The Bad and the Beautiful	1952	Stadt der Illusionen
The Quiet Man	1952	Der Sieger
Roman Holiday	1953	Ein Herz und eine Krone
The Big Heat	1953	Heiße eisen
On the Waterfront	1954	Die Faust im Nacken
Lady and the Tramp	1955	Susi und Strolch
Rebel Without a Cause	1955	...denn sie wissen nicht, was sie tun
To Catch a Thief	1955	Über den Dächern von Nizza
The Killing	1956	Die Rechnung ging nicht auf
Forbidden Planet	1956	Alarm im Weltall
The Searchers	1956	Der schwarze Falke
An Affair to Remember	1957	Die große Liebe meines Lebens
Sweet Smell of Success	1957	Dein Schicksal in meiner Hand
Nort by Northwest	1959	Der unsichtbare Dritte
Les quatre cents coups	1959	Sie küssten und sie schlugen ihn
Peeping Tom	1960	Augen der Angst
The Hustler	1961	Haie der Großstadt
The Innocents	1961	Schloß des Schreckens
The Manchurian Candidate	1962	Botschafter der Angst
To Kill a Mockingbird	1962	Wer die Nachtigall stört
The Great Escape	1963	Gesprengte Ketten
The Sword in the Stone	1963	Die Hexe und der Zauberer
The Haunting	1963	Bis das Blut gefriert
A Hard Day's Night	1964	Yeah, Yeah, Yeah

The Sound of Music	1965	Meine Lieder, meine Träume
A Charlie Brown Christmas	1965	Die Peanuts – Fröhliche Weihnachten
Pierrot le fou	1965	Elf Uhr nachts
Alphaville, une étrange aventure de Lemmy Caution	1965	Lemmy Caution gegen Alpha 60
How the Grinch Stole Christmas!	1966	Die gestohlenen Weihnachtsgeschenke
Il buono, il brutto, il cattivo	1966	Zwei glorreiche Halunken
The Graduate	1967	Die Reifeprüfung
Cool Hand Luke	1967	Der Unbeugsame
The Producers	1967	Frühling für Hitler
Where Eagle Dares	1968	Agenten sterben einsam
C'era una volta il West	1968	Spiel mir das Lied vom Tod
True Gift	1969	Der Marshal
Take the Money and Run	1969	Woody, der Unglücksrabe
Kelly's Heroes	1970	Stoßtrupp Gold
Five Easy Pieces	1970	Ein Mann sucht sich selbst
Straw Dogs	1971	Wer Gewalt sät
Deliverance	1972	Beim Sterben ist jeder der Erste
Sleuth	1972	Mord mit kleinen Fehlern
The Sting	1973	Der Clou
Enter the Dragon	1973	Der Mann mit der Todeskralle
Mean Streets	1973	Hexenkessel
The Texas Chain Saw Massacre	1974	Blutgericht in Texas
Blazing Saddles	1974	Der Wilde Wilde Westen
Death Wish	1974	Ein Mann sieht rot
Jaws	1975	Der weiße Hai
Monty Python and the Holy Grail	1975	Die Ritter der Kokosnuß
All the President's Men	1976	Die Unbestechlichen
The Outlaw Josey Wales	1976	Der Texaner
The Enforcer	1976	Dirty Harry III – Der Unerbittliche
Annie Hall	1977	Der Stadtneurotiker
The Rescuers	1977	Bernard und Bianca – Die Mäusepolizei
Smokey and the Bandit	1977	Ein ausgekochtes Schlitzohr

The Deer Hunter	1978	Die durch die Hölle gehen
Animal House	1978	Ich glaub, mich tritt ein Pferd
Jaws 2	1978	Der weiße Hai 2
Days of Heaven	1978	In der Glut des Südens
The Evil Dead	1981	Tanz der Teufel
Escape from New York	1981	Die Klapperschlange
The Fox and the Hound	1981	Cap und Capper
Stripes	1981	Ich glaub' mich knutscht ein Elch!
First Blood	1982	Rambo
Trading Places	1983	Die Glücksritter
National Lampoon's Vacation	1983	Die schrillen Vier auf Achse
A Nightmare on Elm Street	1984	Nightmare – Mörderische Träume
A View to Kill	1985	James Bond 007 – Im Angesicht des Todes
Evil Dead II	1987	Tanz der Teufel 2 – Jetzt wird noch mehr getanzt
Coming to America	1988	Der Prinz aus Zamunda
Point Break	1991	Gefährliche Brandung
Unforgiven	1992	Erbarmungslos
Home Alone 2: Lost in New York	1992	Kevin – Allein in New York
A Few Good Men	1992	Eine Frage der Ehre
The Fugitive	1993	Auf der Flucht
The Shawshank Redemption	1994	Die Verurteilten
Die Hard with a Vengeance	1995	Stirb langsam – Jetzt erst recht
Face/Off	1997	Im Körper des Feindes
Lock, Stock and the Two Smoking Barrels	1998	Bube Dame König GrAs
A Bug's Life	1998	Das große Krabbeln
Meet the Parents	2000	Meine Braut, ihr Vater und ich
Sen to Chihiro no kamikakushi	2001	Chihiros Reise ins Zauberland
Cidade de Deus	2002	City of God
Pirates of the Caribbean: The Curse of the Black Pearl	2003	Fluch der Karibik
Oldeuboi	2003	Oldboy
Eternal Sunshine of the Spotless Mind	2004	Vergiss mein nicht!
The Notebook	2004	Wie ein einziger Tag

Taken	2008	96 Hours
Despicable Me	2010	Ich – Einfach unverbesserlich
X: First Class	2011	X-Men: Erste Entscheidung
Intouchables	2011	Ziemlich beste Freunde
Frozen	2013	Die Eiskönigin – Völlig unverfroren
Captain America: The Winter Soldier	2014	The Return of the First Avenger

2.4 Transcription

Entr'acte	1924	Entr'acte
Sherlock Jr.	1924	Sherlock jr.
Wings	1927	Wings
The Unknown	1927	The Unknown – Der Unbekannte
Steamboat Bill, Jr.	1928	Steamboat Bill, jr.
Steamboat Willie	1928	Steamboat Willie
The Broadway Melody	1929	The Broadway Melody
Queen Kelly	1929	Queen Kelly
The Cocoanuts	1929	The Cocoanuts
Animal Crackers	1930	Animal Crackers
Frankenstein	1931	Frankenstein
Dracula	1931	Dracula
Tabu: A Story of the South Seas	1931	Tabu
Freaks	1932	Freaks
White Zombie	1932	The White Zombie
King Kong	1933	King Kong und die weiße Frau
L'Atalante	1934	Atalante
Anna Karenina	1935	Anna Karenina
Swing Time	1936	Swing Time
Reefer Madness	1936	Reefer Madness
Aleksandr Nevskiy	1938	Alexander Newski

Jezebel	1938	Jezebel – Die boshafte Lady
Ninotchka	1939	Ninotchka
Fantasia	1940	Fantasia
Pinocchio	1940	Pinocchio
Rebecca	1940	Rebecca
Sergeant York	1941	Sergeant York
Dumbo	1941	Dumbo, der fliegende Elefant
Yankee Doodle Dandy	1942	Yankee Doodle Dandy
Casablanca	1942	Casablanca
Bambi	1942	Bambi
Mrs. Miniver	1942	Mrs. Miniver
Sahara	1943	Sahara
Jane Eyre	1943	Jane Eyre – Die Waise von Lowood
Laura	1944	Laura
Meet Me in St. Louis	1944	Meet me in St. Louis
Gilda	1947	Gilda
Monsieur Verdoux	1947	Monsieur Verdoux – Der Frauenmörder von Paris
Red River	1948	Red River
Hamlet	1948	Hamlet
Cinderella	1950	Cinderella
Winchester '73	1950	Winchester '73
Rio Grande	1950	Rio Grande
Sunset Blvd.	1950	Sunset Blvd. – Boulevard der Dämmerung
Harvey	1950	Mein Freund Harvey
The African Queen	1951	African Queen
Umberto D.	1952	Umberto D.
Ikiru	1952	Ikiru – Einmal wirklich leben
Stalag 17	1953	Stalag 17
Peter Pan	1953	Peter Pan
Shane	1953	Mein großer Freund Shane
Sabrina	1954	Sabrina
Gojira	1954	Godzilla

La strada	1954	La Strada – Das Lied der Straße
The Ladykillers	1955	Ladykillers
Dracula	1958	Dracula
Gigi	1958	Gigi
The Blob	1958	Blob – Schrecken ohne Namen
Vertigo	1958	Vertigo – Aus dem Reich der Toten
Hiroshima mon amour	1959	Hiroshima mon amour
Ben-Hur	1959	Ben Hur
Rio Bravo	1959	Rio Bravo
Psycho	1960	Psycho
Spartacus	1960	Spartacus
West Side Story	1961	West Side Story
Viridiana	1961	Viridiana
Yôjinbô	1961	Yojimbo – Der Leibwächter
Lolita	1962	Lolita
La jetée	1962	La jetée – Am Rande des Rollfelds
Dr. No	1962	James Bond 007 jagt Dr. No
Cleopatra	1963	Cleopatra
Charade	1963	Charade
Mary Poppins	1964	Mary Poppins
Marnie	1964	Marnie
My Fair Lady	1964	My Fair Lady
Goldfinger	1964	James Bond 007 – Goldfinger
Zulu	1964	Zulu – Die Schlacht von Rorkes Drift
Manos: The Hands of Fate	1966	Manos: The Hands of Fate
Persona	1966	Persona
Fahrenheit 451	1966	Fahrenheit 451
Andrey Rublev	1966	Andrej Rubljow
Blowup	1966	BlowUp – Ekstaze '67
Chitty Chitty Bang Bang	1968	Tschitti Tschitti Bäng Bäng
Bullitt	1968	Bullitt
Easy Rider	1969	Easy Rider

The Wild Bunch	1969	The Wild Bunch – Sie kannten kein Gesetz
Z	1969	Z – Anatomie eines politischen Mordes
Butch Cassidy and the Sundance Kid	1969	Butch Cassidy und Sundance Kid – Zwei Banditen
The AristoCats	1970	Aristocats
MASH	1970	M.A.S.H.
Little Big Man	1970	Little Big Man
Love Story	1970	Love Story
El Topo	1970	El Topo
Tora! Tora! Tora!	1970	Tora! Tora! Tora!
Patton	1970	Patton – Rebell in Uniform
Dirty Harry	1971	Dirty Harry
Harold and Maude	1971	Harold and Maude
THX 1138	1971	THX 1138
The French Connection	1971	French Connection – Brennpunkt Brooklyn
Cabaret	1972	Cabaret
Frenzy	1972	Frenzy
Solyaris	1972	Solaris
Robin Hood	1973	Robin Hood
Serpico	1973	Serpico
American Graffiti	1973	American Graffiti
The Wicker Man	1973	The Wicker Man
Papillon	1973	Papillon
Chinatown	1974	Chinatown
The Rocky Horror Picture Show	1975	The Rocky Horror Picture Show
Barry Lyndon	1975	Barry Lyndon
Sholay	1975	Sholay
Taxi Driver	1976	Taxi Driver
Rocky	1976	Rocky
Network	1976	Network
Carrie	1976	Carrie – Des Satans jüngste Tochter
Eraserhead	1977	Eraserhead
Suspiria	1977	Suspiria

Grease	1978	Grease
Superman	1978	Superman
Halloween	1978	Halloween – Die Nacht des Grauens
Dawn of the Dead	1978	Zombie – Dawn of the Dead
Midnight Express	1978	12 Uhr nachts – Midnight Express
Apocalypse Now	1979	Apocalypse Now
The Warriors	1979	Die Warriors
Mad Max	1979	Mad Max
Rocky II	1979	Rocky II
Alien	1979	Alien – Das unheimliche Wesen aus einer fremden Welt
Moonraker	1979	James Bond 007 – Moonraker – Streng geheim
Superman II	1980	Superman 2
Caddyshack	1980	Caddyshack – Wahnsinn ohne Handicap
Superman II	1980	Superman II – Allein gegen alle
The Shining	1980	Shining
The Blues Brothers	1980	Blues Brothers
Mad Max 2	1981	Mad Max II – Der Vollstrecker
Halloween II	1981	Halloween II – Das Grauen kehrt zurück
An American Werewolf in London	1981	American Werewolf
Blade Runner	1982	Blade Runner
Poltergeist	1982	Poltergeist
TRON	1982	Tron
Gandhi	1982	Gandhi
Rocky III	1982	Rocky III – Das Auge des Tigers
Scarface	1983	Scarface
Videodrome	1983	Videodrome
Octopussy	1983	James Bond 007 – Octopussy
WarGames	1983	WarGames – Kriegsspiele
This Is Spinal Tap	1984	This Is Spinal Tap
Ghostbusters	1984	Ghostbusters – Die Geisterjäger
Gremlins	1984	Gremlins – Kleine Monster
Beverly Hills Cop	1984	Beverly Hills Cop – Ich lös' den Fall auf jeden Fall

The Karate Kid	1984	Karate Kid
The Terminator	1984	Terminator
Brazil	1985	Brazil
Ran	1985	Ran
Rocky IV	1985	Rocky IV – Der Kampf des Jahrhunderts
The Breakfast Club	1985	Breakfast Club – Der Frühstücksclub
Platoon	1986	Platoon
Blue Velvet	1986	Blue Velvet
Aliens	1986	Aliens – Die Rückkehr
Stand by Me	1986	Stand by Me – Das Geheimnis eines Sommers
Top Gun	1986	Top Gun – Sie fürchten weder Tod noch Teufel
Highlander	1986	Highlander – Es kann nur einen geben
RoboCop	1987	RoboCop
Full Metal Jacket	1987	Full Metal Jacket
Predator	1987	Predator
Dirty Dancing	1987	Dirty Dancing
Spaceballs	1987	Spaceballs
Wall Street	1987	Wall Street
The Untouchables	1987	The Untouchables – Die Unbestechlichen
Lethal Weapon	1987	Lethal Weapon – Zwei stahlharte Profis
Rain Man	1988	Rain Man
Big	1988	Big
Beetlejuice	1988	Beetlejuice
Nuovo Cinema Paradiso	1988	Cinema paradiso
Ghostbusters II	1989	Ghostbusters 2
The Abyss	1989	The Abyss
Batman	1989	Batman
Lethal Weapon 2	1989	Lethal Weapon 2 – Brennpunkt L.A.
Pretty Woman	1990	Pretty Woman
Total Recall	1990	Die totale Erinnerung – Total Recall
Ghost	1990	Ghost – Nachricht von Sam
Goodfellas	1990	GoodFellas – Drei Jahrzehnte in der Mafia

Hook	1991	Hook
Thelma & Louise	1991	Thelma & Louise
JFK	1991	JFK – Tatort Dallas
The Addams Family	1991	Die Addams Family
Reservoir Dogs	1992	Reservoir Dogs
Aladdin	1992	Aladdin
Alien ³	1992	Alien ³
Basic Instinct	1992	Basic Instinct
Dracula	1992	Bram Stoker's Dracula
True Romance	1993	True Romance
Jurassic Park	1993	Jurassic Park
Philadelphia	1993	Philadelphia
Mrs. Doubtfire	1993	Mrs. Doubtfire – Das stachelige Kindermädchen
Clerks	1993	Clerks – Die Ladenhüter
The Nightmare Before Christmas	1993	Nightmare Before Christmas
Pulp Fiction	1994	Pulp Fiction
Forrest Gump	1994	Forrest Gump
Speed	1994	Speed
Léon	1994	Léon – Der Profi
Braveheart	1995	Braveheart
Toy Story	1995	Toy Story
Heat	1995	Heat
Casino	1995	Casino
Apollo 13	1995	Apollo 13
Jumanji	1995	Jumanji
Twelve Monkeys	1995	12 Monkeys
Fargo	1996	Fargo
Independence Day	1996	Independence Day
Mission: Impossible	1996	Mission: Impossible
From Dusk Till Dawn	1996	From Dusk Till Dawn
Mars Attacks!	1996	Mars Attacks!
Trainspotting	1996	Trainspotting – Neue Helden

The Rock	1996	The Rock – Fels der Entscheidung
Scream	1996	Scream – Schrei!
Jerry Maguire	1996	Jerry Maguire – Spiel des Lebens
Romeo + Juliet	1996	William Shakespeares Romeo + Julia
Titanic	1997	Titanic
Good Will Hunting	1997	Good Will Hunting
L.A. Confidential	1997	L.A. Confidential
Men in Black	1997	Men in Black
The Game	1997	The Game
American History X	1998	American History X
The Big Lebowski	1998	The Big Lebowski
Fear and Loathing in Las Vegas	1998	Fear and Loathing in Las Vegas
Blade	1998	Blade
Armageddon	1998	Armageddon – Das jüngste Gericht
Fight Club	1999	Fight Club
American Beauty	1999	American Beauty
The Green Mile	1999	The Green Mile
The Sixth Sense	1999	The Sixth Sense
Toy Story 2	1999	Toy Story 2
Sleepy Hollow	1999	Sleepy Hollow
American Pie	1999	American Pie – Wie ein heißer Apfelkuchen
The Matrix	1999	Matrix
Requiem for a Dream	2000	Requiem for a Dream
American Psycho	2000	American Psycho
Mission: Impossible II	2000	Mission: Impossible 2
Snatch	2000	Snatch – Schweine und Diamanten
X-Men	2000	X-Men – Der Film
Cast Away	2000	Cast Away – Verschollen
Unbreakable	2000	Unbreakable – Unzerbrechlich
Donnie Darko	2001	Donnie Darko
Ocean's Eleven	2001	Ocean's Eleven
Training Day	2001	Training Day

Gladiator	2001	Gladiator
Memento	2001	Memento
A Beautiful Mind	2001	A Beautiful Mind – Genie und Wahnsinn
Shrek	2001	Shrek – Der tollkühne Held
Spider-Man	2002	Spider-Man
Catch Me If You Can	2002	Catch Me If You Can
Minority Report	2002	Minority Report
Ice Age	2002	Ice Age
Kill Bill: Vol. 1	2003	Kill Bill: Volume 1
Big Fish	2003	Big Fish
Mystic River	2003	Mystic River
X-Men 2	2003	X-Men 2
The Matrix Reloaded	2003	Matrix Reloaded
The Matrix Revolutions	2003	Matrix Revolutions
Kill Bill: Vol. 2	2004	Kill Bill – Volume 2
Million Dollar Baby	2004	Million Dollar Baby
Spider-Man 2	2004	Spider-Man 2
Shaun of the Dead	2004	Shaun of the Dead
I, Robot	2004	I, Robot
The Incredibles	2004	Die Unglaublichen – The Incredibles
Batman Begins	2005	Batman Begins
Sin City	2005	Sin City
Mr. & Mrs. Smith	2005	Mr. & Mrs. Smith
King Kong	2005	King Kong
300	2006	300
Blood Diamond	2006	Blood Diamond
Children of Men	2006	Children of Men
Little Miss Sunshine	2006	Little Miss Sunshine
The Departed	2006	Departed – Unter Feinden
Casino Royale	2006	James Bond 007 – Casino Royale
The Prestige	2006	Prestige – Die Meister der Magie
Pirates of the Caribbean: Dead Man's Chest	2006	Pirates of the Caribbean – Fluch der Karibik 2

No Country for Old Men	2007	No Country for Old Men
I Am Legend	2007	I Am Legend
Transformers	2007	Transformers
Ratatouille	2007	Ratatouille
Into the Wild	2007	Into the Wild
Superbad	2007	Superbad
Juno	2007	Juno
Spider-Man 3	2007	Spider-Man 3
The Dark Knight	2008	The Dark Knight
Iron Man	2008	Iron Man
Gran Torino	2008	Gran Torino
Hancock	2008	Hancock
WALL·E	2008	WALL·E – Der Letzte räumt die Erde auf
Twilight	2008	Twilight – Biss zum Morgengrauen
Inglourious Basterds	2009	Inglourious Basterds
Star Trek	2009	Star Trek
Sherlock Holmes	2009	Sherlock Holmes
Zombieland	2009	Zombieland
(500) Days of Summer	2009	(500) Days of Summer
Avatar	2009	Avatar – Aufbruch nach Pandora
Watchmen	2009	Watchmen – Die Wächter
The Hangover	2009	Hangover
The District 9	2009	District 9
Inception	2010	Inception
Shutter Island	2010	Shutter Island
Black Swan	2010	Black Swan
Toy Story 3	2010	Toy Story 3
Iron Man 2	2010	Iron Man 2
The Social Network	2010	The Social Network
Kick-Ass	2010	Kick-Ass
The King's Speech	2010	The King's Speech – Die Rede des Königs
Thor	2011	Thor

Captain America: The First Avenger	2011	Captain America – The First Avenger
Drive	2011	Drive
Source Code	2011	Source Code
The Hangover Part II	2011	Hangover 2
The Dark Knight Rises	2012	The Dark Knight Rises
The Avengers	2012	The Avengers
Django Unchained	2012	Django Unchained
Ted	2012	Ted
Argo	2012	Argo
Skyfall	2012	James Bond 007 – Skyfall
Prometheus	2012	Prometheus – Dunkle Zeichen
The Hunger Games	2012	Die Tribute von Panem – The Hunger Games
Silver Linings Playbook	2012	Silver Linings
The Wolf of Wall Street	2013	The Wolf of Wall Street
Gravity	2013	Gravity
Iron Man Three	2013	Iron Man 3
Man of Steel	2013	Man of Steel
World War Z	2013	World War Z
12 Years a Slave	2013	12 Years a Slave
Now You See Me	2013	Die Unfassbaren – Now You See Me
The Hunger Games: Catching Fire	2013	Die Tribute von Panem – Catching Fire
Interstellar	2014	Interstellar
Guardians of the Galaxy	2014	Guardians of the Galaxy
Edge of Tomorrow	2014	Edge of Tomorrow
Whiplash	2014	Whiplash
Kingsman: The Secret Service	2014	Kingsman: The Secret Service
Gone Girl	2014	Gone Girl – Das perfekte Opfer
The Imitation Game	2014	The Imitation Game – Ein streng geheimes Leben
X-Men: Days of Future Past	2014	X-Men: Zukunft ist Vergangenheit
Mad Max: Fury Road	2015	Mad Max: Fury Road
Avengers: Age of Ultron	2015	Avengers: Age of Ultron
Jurassic World	2015	Jurassic World

Ant-Man	2015	Ant-Man
The Hateful Eight	2015	The Hateful 8
Ex Machina	2015	Ex Machina
The Revenant	2015	The Revenant – Der Rückkehrer
Deadpool	2016	Deadpool
Batman v Superman: Dawn of Justice	2016	Batman v Superman: Dawn of Justice
Suicide Squad	2016	Suicide Squad
Arrival	2016	Arrival
Rogue One: A Star Wars Story	2016	Rogue One: A Star Wars Story
Doctor Strange	2016	Doctor Strange
X-Men: Apocalypse	2016	X-Men: Apocalypse
La La Land	2016	La La Land
Captain America: Civil War	2016	The First Avenger: Civil War
Wonder Woman	2017	Wonder Woman
Guardians of the Galaxy Vol. 2	2017	Guardians of the Galaxy Vol. 2
Dunkirk	2017	Dunkirk
Spider-Man: Homecoming	2017	Spider-Man: Homecoming
Baby Driver	2017	Baby Driver
Get Out	2017	Get Out
Logan	2017	Logan – The Wolverine

2.5 CTTs

Mr. Smith Goes to Washington	1939	Mr. Smith geht nach Washington
The Lost World: Jurassic Park	1997	Vergessene Welt – Jurassic Park
Star Wars: Episode I – The Phantom Menace	1999	Star Wars: Episode I – Die dunkle Bedrohung
Star Wars: Episode II – Attack of the Clones	2002	Star Wars: Episode II – Angriff der Klonkrieger
Star Wars: Episode III – Revenge of the Sith	2005	Star Wars: Episode III – Die Rache der Sith
X-Men: The Last Stand	2006	X-Men: Der letzte Widerstand
Pirates of the Caribbean: At World's End	2007	Pirates of the Caribbean – Am Ende der Welt

Slumdog Millionaire	2008	Slumdog Millionär
Star Wars: Episode VII – The Force Awakens	2015	Star Wars: Episode VII – Das Erwachen der Macht

Appendix 2

Translation strategies in the Croatian subcorpus

Graph 1

Translation strategies in the German subcorpus

Graph 2

Free translations in the Croatian subcorpus

Graph 3

Transcriptions in the Croatian subcorpus

Graph 4

Free translations in the German subcorpus

Graph 5

Transcriptions in the Croatian subcorpus

Graph 6

Croatian translations, 1928–1937

Graph 7

Croatian translations, 1938–1947

Graph 8

Croatian translations, 1948–1957

Graph 9

Croatian translations, 1958–1967

Graph 10

Croatian translations, 1968–1977

Graph 11

Croatian translations, 1978–1987

Graph 12

Croatian translations, 1988–1997

Graph 13

Croatian translations, 1998–2007

Graph 14

Croatian translations, 2008–2017

Graph 15

German translations, 1928–1937

Graph 16

German translations, 1938–1947

Graph 17

German translations, 1948–1957

Graph 18

German translations, 1958–1967

Graph 19

German translations, 1968–1977

Graph 20

German translations, 1978–1987

Graph 21

German translations, 1988–1997

Graph 22

German translations, 1998–2007

Graph 23

German translations, 2008–2017

Graph 24